

Zurich University of Applied Science (ZHAW)

Life Sciences and Facility Management

Institute of Environment and Natural Resources

**An agri-food value chain analysis with a focus on
environmental and economic impacts of hydroponics:
A case study on tomato cultivation in Morocco**

Master Thesis

by

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Field of study: Master in Environment and Natural Resources with focus on Agroecology and Food Systems

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Zürich, 27 June 2024

Imprint

Keywords:

Tomato, hydroponics, value chain analysis, LCA, profitability, Morocco, VCA4D

Recommended form of citation:

Kappeler, A. (2024). An agri-food value chain analysis with a focus on environmental and economic impacts of hydroponics: A case study on tomato cultivation in Morocco. Master Thesis. Zurich University of Applied Science.

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Acknowledgements

I am profoundly thankful for the unwavering support and guidance of my supervisors, Raushan Bokusheva, Franziska Stössel, and Gertrud Buchenrieder, throughout my master's thesis. Their expertise and insightful feedback have been instrumental in shaping this work.

I am deeply grateful to Gertrud Buchenrieder, the project coordinator of the EU-funded research project FrontAg Nexus (<https://frontagnexus.eu/>), for providing me the opportunity to conduct my master's thesis at Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) in collaboration with FrontAg Nexus.

My gratitude also extends to University Mohamed VI Polytechnic (UM6P) for hosting me on their campus, offering me the opportunity to conduct my research in Morocco, and generously providing resources and support. Special thanks to Abdallah Oukarroum, Mohamed Chtouki, and Bouchra Darkaoui, whose exceptional support greatly contributed to this work.

Lastly, I would like to acknowledge all the participants who contributed to this research. Their involvement and cooperation have been crucial in achieving the objectives of this study.

Thank you all for your invaluable contributions.

Anina Kappeler

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Abstract

Today's agri-food system faces diverse challenges, such as social and environmental costs caused by increased agricultural productivity or the impact of climate change on agriculture. Moreover, globalisation leads to an increase in international trade, and modern agricultural technologies, such as hydroponics, offer potential solutions to the challenges in agriculture. The aim of this thesis is to analyse an agri-food value chain and to understand and quantify the economic and environmental factors of hydroponics. We studied hydroponic tomato farming in Morocco as a case study. The study addresses the following questions: How is the value chain of hydroponic tomatoes in Morocco organised? Is hydroponic tomato farming a financial opportunity for farmers in Morocco compared to traditional soil-based farming, and how does it impact the country? What are the environmental impacts of hydroponic tomatoes compared to traditional soil-based farming? Using the EU's Value Chain Analysis for Development (VCA4D) approach, the study combines qualitative and quantitative assessments. First, this includes an analysis of the value chain to gain an overview of the processes and actors involved. Second, it involves an economic analysis at three levels: the farm business, the national economy, and competitiveness in the international context. Third, it includes an environmental impact assessment focusing on human health, ecosystem quality, and resource depletion.

The analysis shows that hydroponic tomato production in Morocco is embedded in a well-organised value chain integrated into the European market. Hydroponic tomatoes are a crucial export product and income source for farmers and the national economy. Due to higher productivity, hydroponic installations reduce water footprints and increase revenues and profits compared to traditional soil based cultivation. In particular, closed-loop hydroponics reduces the overall environmental impact through improved water and fertiliser use efficiency.

We conclude that hydroponics, especially closed-loop systems, offer technical solutions to address certain environmental problems, open market opportunities and can increase income. However, market fluctuations and susceptibility to pests and diseases remain a pressure in the current system.

Zusammenfassung

Das heutige Agrar- und Lebensmittelsystem steht vor vielfältigen Herausforderungen, wie zum Beispiel die Steigerung der landwirtschaftlichen Produktivität, die häufig negative soziale und ökologische Folgen hat, oder der Einfluss vom Klimawandel. Gleichzeitig wächst durch die Globalisierung der internationale Agrarhandel stetig und landwirtschaftliche Techniken wie Hydroponik, auch bekannt als Hors-sol, sollen potenzielle Lösungen für Herausforderungen wie Wasserknappheit in der Landwirtschaft im Zusammenhang mit dem Klimawandel bieten und diese mildern.

Das Ziel dieser Masterarbeit ist es, eine Wertschöpfungskette im Agrar- und Lebensmittelsektor zu analysieren und zu untersuchen, wie Hydroponik die Umwelt und die wirtschaftliche Situation von Landwirt:innen beeinflusst. Dabei dient der Tomatenanbau in Marokko als Fallstudie. Folgende Forschungsfragen werden adressiert: Wie ist die Wertschöpfungskette von hydroponisch angebauten Tomaten in Marokko organisiert? Welche finanziellen Chancen bietet der hydroponische Tomatenanbau marokkanischen Landwirt:innen im Vergleich zum traditionellen Anbau im Boden und wie wirkt sich dies auf das Land aus? Welche ökologischen Auswirkungen hat der hydroponische Tomatenanbau im Vergleich zum traditionellen Anbau im Boden? Die vorliegende Arbeit orientiert sich am *Value Chain Analysis for Development* (VCA4D) Ansatz der EU und kombiniert qualitative und quantitative Bewertungsmethoden. Sie umfasst eine Analyse der Wertschöpfungskette, um einen Überblick über die beteiligten Prozesse und Akteur:innen zu erhalten. Darüber hinaus erfolgt eine ökonomische Analyse auf drei Ebenen: dem landwirtschaftlichen Betrieb, der nationalen Wirtschaft und der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit im internationalen Kontext. Zusätzlich wird eine Umweltbewertung durchgeführt, die sich auf die menschliche Gesundheit, die Qualität der Ökosysteme und die Ressourcenerschöpfung konzentriert.

Die Analyse zeigt, dass die hydroponische Tomatenproduktion in Marokko in eine gut organisierte Wertschöpfungskette eingebettet ist, die eine enge Zusammenarbeit mit dem europäischen Markt beinhaltet. Tomaten spielen eine bedeutende Rolle im Export und stellen eine zentrale Einkommensquelle für die Landwirt:innen und die nationale Wirtschaft dar. Die hydroponische Anbautechnik reduziert den Wasserverbrauch und steigert die Einnahmen sowie die finanziellen Gewinne im Vergleich zum traditionellen Anbau aufgrund der höheren Produktivität. Insbesondere Hydroponiksysteme mit geschlossenem Kreislauf verringern die Umweltbelastung durch effiziente Nutzung von Wasser und Dünger. Offene Systeme hingegen,

bei denen überschüssiges Wasser abläuft, zeigen ähnliche Umweltauswirkungen wie traditionelle Anbausysteme, bieten jedoch im Vergleich trotzdem den Vorteil eines verbesserten Wasserverbrauchs. Zusammenfassend lässt sich feststellen, dass hydroponische Systeme bestimmte Umweltprobleme angehen, neue Marktchancen ermöglichen und die Einkommenssteigerung fördern können. Im derzeitigen System bleibt allerdings der Marktdruck und die Anfälligkeit auf Schädlinge und Krankheiten eine Belastung.

Table of Content

List of Figures	VI
List of Tables.....	VII
List of Abbreviations.....	VIII
1 Introduction.....	1
2 Conceptual framework and selection of method	3
2.1 Value chain analysis.....	3
2.2 Selection of method.....	5
3 Methodology.....	7
3.1 Data collection.....	7
3.2 Functional analysis (RQ1).....	8
3.3 Economic analysis (RQ2).....	8
3.3.1 Profitability of farm businesses	8
3.3.2 Total effects within the national economy.....	9
3.3.3 Competitiveness in the international context.....	10
3.4 Life Cycle Assessment (RQ3).....	10
3.4.1 Goal and scope definition	11
3.4.2 Life cycle inventory	14
3.4.3 Impact assessment.....	18
4 Results.....	19
4.1 Functional analysis (RQ1).....	19
4.1.1 Value chain overview	19
4.1.2 Tomato cultivation techniques	22
4.1.3 Contextual information	24
4.2 Economic analysis (RQ2).....	27
4.2.1 Profitability of farm businesses	27

4.2.2	Total effects within the national economy.....	31
4.2.3	Competitiveness in the international context.....	32
4.3	Life cycle impact assessment (RQ3).....	34
4.3.1	ReCiPe.....	34
4.3.2	IPCC 2021.....	38
4.3.3	AWARE.....	39
5	Discussion.....	40
5.1	Synthesis of the results.....	40
5.2	Recommendations.....	44
5.3	Limitations and future research.....	46
6	Conclusion.....	47
	Bibliography.....	IX
	Appendices.....	XIX
	Statement of Authorship.....	XLV

List of Figures

Figure 1: System boundary of the LCA	13
Figure 2: Value chain overview	20
Figure 3: Hydroponic tomato cultivation in coco coir substrate	22
Figure 4: Relative contribution of each case compared to the case with the highest impact to each damage (=endpoint) category	35
Figure 5: Relative contribution of the value chain steps to each damage category	36
Figure 6: Relative contribution of each case to GWP 100	38
Figure 7: Relative contribution of each case to the water footprint	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the key inventory data	15
Table 2: Irrigation scenarios for case 1 and case 2	16
Table 3: Composition of average N-fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)	17
Table 4: Composition of average P ₂ O ₅ -fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)	17
Table 5: Composition of average K ₂ O-fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)	17
Table 6: Description of the endpoint levels including the corresponding midpoint levels (adjusted from Fabre et al. (2021) and Huijbregts et al., 2017)	19
Table 7: Relative agricultural expenses for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation	29
Table 8: Relative expenses in the value chain for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation.....	29
Table 9: GOP for the four cases of tomato production	30
Table 10: Total damage of each case to each damage (=endpoint) category	34
Table 11: Absolute contribution of the value chain steps to each damage category	37
Table 12: Absolute water footprint of all the cases.....	39

List of Abbreviations

FU	Functional Unit
GOP	Gross Operating Profit
GWP	Global Warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MAD	Moroccan Dirhams
NPC	Normalized Price Coefficient
RQ	Research Question
ToBRFV	Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus
VA	Value Added
VCA4D	Value Chain Analysis for Development

1 Introduction

Today's agri-food system faces diverse challenges. In the last decades, increased agricultural productivity, such as high-yield crop varieties, has been recorded to satisfy the food demand of a growing global population (FAO, 2018; Stewart, 2023). However, this development has often come with significant social and environmental costs (FAO, 2018). Agriculture is a major contributor to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, soil degradation, biodiversity loss, ecosystem stress, and water scarcity (IPCC, 2019; Poore & Nemecek, 2018). The sector not only negatively impacts the environment but is also highly affected by the changes (FAO, 2023; World Bank, 2023). In particular, climate change causes annual damage and losses in agriculture due to extreme weather events such as droughts and heavy rainfall (FAO, 2023). Different regions worldwide are affected dissimilarly by climate change, with Africa, Asia, and parts of Latin America typically seen as the most vulnerable (IPCC, 2012).

Simultaneously, agricultural development comes along with a strong growth in global agri-food trade as a result of globalisation (Barrett et al., 2022; FAO, 2020; OECD, 2020). Since 1995, the volume of international trade in food and agriculture has more than doubled, with emerging and developing economies accounting for one-third of total exports (FAO, 2020). Growth in trade is noted in various soft commodities, including cereals, oilseeds, fruit, and vegetables (WTO, n.d.). It is argued that export opportunities through international trade are important for the livelihoods of farmers and people employed throughout the agri-food value chain and to help decrease global food insecurity (OECD, n.d.). However, the increased role of global value chains matters in the discussion of the environmental sustainability of agri-food systems (Deconinck & Toyama, 2022).

In this context, developing a resilient and sustainable agri-food system is essential (World Bank, 2023). Modern agricultural techniques are evolving and aim to mitigate climatic factors, such as droughts that affect agriculture, and offer potential solutions (Hemathilake & Gunathilake, 2022). Recent developments include genetically modified crops and new farming techniques for growing plants without soil (Stewart, 2023): such as hydroponics (in which plant roots reside in a nutrient solution or substrate (Maucieri et al., 2019)), aquaponics (which combine hydroponics with aquaculture (Maucieri et al., 2019)), and aeroponics (in which plant roots are sprayed with water and nutrients (Hemathilake & Gunathilake, 2022)). Studies highlight the

advantages of modern technologies, such as the water-saving capacity of hydroponics (Grewal et al., 2011; Ntinis et al., 2017). Yet they are a topic of growing concern, studies highlight the environmental risks associated with such methods, specifically emissions related to the substantial electricity requirements for temperature control and artificial lighting (Gołasa et al., 2021; Mahdavian & Wattanapongsakorn, 2017).

In addition to the scientific nature of these questions, consumer awareness, state-enforced regulations, and transparency initiatives, such as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), increase. This results in a rising pressure on firms. They are now expected to take responsibility for environmental impacts throughout the entire value chain, rather than just within their own operations (Bröskamp & Simon, 2023; Deconinck & Hobeika, 2022; EQS, 2024). Studies can help inform stakeholders and policymakers about sustainability in value chains to improve transparency and facilitate decision-making.

The aim of this thesis is to conduct an analysis of an agri-food value chain and to understand and quantify the economic and environmental factors of hydroponics. For this study, we focus on Morocco, a region increasingly involved in global trade, and also affected by severe droughts due to climate change (World Bank, 2023). We use hydroponic tomato farming as a case study. The research questions (RQ) are as follows: First, RQ1: How is the value chain of hydroponic tomatoes in Morocco organised? Second, RQ2: Is hydroponic tomato farming a financial opportunity for farmers in Morocco compared to traditional soil-based farming, and how does it impact the country? Third, RQ3: What are the environmental impacts of hydroponic tomatoes compared to traditional soil-based farming?

The methodology used to achieve the thesis's objective is based on the EU's Value Chain Analysis for Development (VCA4D) approach, specifically designed to address complex questions in the agri-food system. The method is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments (Fabre et al., 2021). VCA4D is a qualified tool to analyse agri-food value chains (Cristino Mandinga Bonfim et al., 2019). First, this includes a qualitative assessment of the value chain to gain an overview of the processes and actors involved to answer RQ1. Second, it involves an economic analysis at three levels: the farm business, the national economy, and competitiveness in the international context, to answer RQ2. In addition

to a qualitative description of the economic situation, the economic analysis is based on a calculation of the Gross Operating Profit (GOP), an evaluation of the contribution of the tomato value chain to GDP, and a calculation of the Normalized Price Coefficient (NPC) to assess competitiveness in the international context. Third, it includes an environmental impact assessment focusing on human health, ecosystem quality, and resource depletion to answer RQ3. The environmental impact is calculated using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Therefore, this thesis can be valuable for stakeholders and policymakers to understand the impact of modern cultivation methods and their economic and environmental implications to sustainably transform the agri-food system in global agri-food value chains.

The case study was conducted in collaboration with an EU-funded research project, FrontAg Nexus.

The underlying study's structure is divided into six chapters. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the conceptual framework and explains the reason behind the selection of the method. This is followed by a detailed description of the methodology in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 presents the results, which are discussed in Chapter 5. Additionally, Chapter 5 includes recommendations, limitations, and further research ideas. Finally, a conclusion is drawn in the last chapter.

2 Conceptual framework and selection of method

2.1 Value chain analysis

The value chain concept emerged in the 1930s within the industrial sector, describing a series of activities connecting upstream and downstream participants involved in the production, transformation, and distribution of goods and services. Over time, this concept has evolved, but it has not led to a universally accepted definition or a singular analytical method (Clay & Feeney, 2019; Rastoin & Ghersi, 2010). However, various approaches exist to analyse value chains, each with specific objectives and uses. Some are rooted in theoretical frameworks, while others focus on practical or operational applications (Dabat et al., 2018). These approaches analyse the interactions within value chains differently: some emphasise functional linkages related to input/output and flow management, while others focus on the coordination among actors (Lançon et al., 2016). Three primary research streams can be identified in the value chain

literature (The Anh et al., 2008): (i) The “Filière” Approach: This concept examines the sequence of activities from raw materials to finished products (Durufle et al., 1988). (ii) Porter's Value Chain Framework: Porter identifies primary and support activities in value creation (Porter, 1985). (iii) Global Value Chain Approach: This approach explores the global organisation and governance of value chains (Gereffi et al., 2005; Kaplinsky, 2000). Overall, Clay and Feeney (2019) identify the following main characteristics of value chain concepts:

- Inputs, outputs, and activities that generate transformation.
- Agents that carry out specific activities and have both vertical and horizontal connections.
- Value addition activities and value allocation.
- A final product or set of final products.
- A group of consumers at the end of the chain.
- Common problems and opportunities shared by all agents.
- Power relations and governance mechanisms.

The literature and evaluation tools for value chain analysis have primarily focused on economic and market aspects (Fabre, 1994; Kaplinsky & Morris, 2001; The Anh et al., 2008). Some authors have integrated social aspects such as poverty reduction (Lundy et al., 2004), impacts on smallholders (Bourgeois & Herrera, 2000), community and gender issues, and environmental aspects (Dabat et al., 2018). Assessing the environmental and social consequences of value chain activities is essential to mitigating their impacts on natural resources and ecosystems and to enhancing their social effects. It is argued that to support sustainable agri-based value chains, social, economic, and environmental dimensions must be considered (Dabat et al., 2018; Deconinck & Hobeika, 2022).

This brings us to the VCA4D framework, recently developed by the EU and Agrinatura, an alliance of European universities dedicated to agricultural research and education for development. This method comprehensively addresses agri-based value chains by examining all three pillars of sustainability (Fabre et al., 2021). Consistent with the “filière” approach, VCA4D views value chains as a sequence of production processes from initial primary production to end use, involving a system of market-oriented actors (Dabat et al., 2018). VCA4D measures key indicators that provide information on a value chain’s impact and

sustainability. Studies provide insights into the impacts generated within the selected country, and if necessary, they can supplement with analyses of activities beyond national borders. The value chain analysis provides a picture of the value chain for a given year, which can be updated to assess its evolution over time. The concept was developed specifically to inform policymakers (Fabre et al., 2021). Some researchers recognise VCA4D as the most updated tool for analysing agri-food value chains (e.g., Cristino Mandinga Bonfim et al., 2019) .

2.2 Selection of method

The VCA4D framework by Fabre et al. (2021) has been selected for this study due to its comprehensive approach to analysing value chains in the agri-food sector, including both environmental and economic impacts. This is align with the focus of this research. Additionally, VCA4D is gaining popularity in literature (e.g., Basset-Mens et al., 2022; Dosso et al., 2024).

The VCA4D framework begins with an exhaustive functional analysis of the value chain and addresses four key framing questions (FQ1 – FQ4):

- FQ1: What is the contribution of the value chain to economic growth?
- FQ2: Is this economic growth inclusive?
- FQ3: Is this value chain socially sustainable?
- FQ4: Is this value chain environmentally sustainable?

Different approaches are used to address these framing questions. For FQ1, various economic indicators are analysed to determine the profitability and sustainability for actors, the total effects within the national economy, and the competitiveness and viability within the international economy. For FQ2, economic indicators are employed to assess income distribution within the value chain. For FQ3, different social themes are evaluated to determine social sustainability. For FQ4, a LCA is conducted to evaluate the environmental impact.

In this study, the functional analysis is instrumental in answering RQ1. Additionally, FQ1 and FQ4 provide insights to answer RQ2 and RQ3, respectively. It is important to note that the framework's FQ2 and FQ3 are not the main focus of this master thesis.

The functional analysis aims to build an overall description of the value chain system. It identifies and characterizes the main actors and stakeholders involved, and it expands on some of the main strategic development challenges faced. This analysis sets the scope for all subsequent analyses to address the framing questions. Essential elements include determining the typology of actors, the sub-chains, and the geographic and time frames.

The environmental assessment for FQ4 involves conducting an LCA, which is a widely used framework in recent literature (Chomkhamsri et al., 2012). LCA evaluates the environmental impacts of a product or system throughout its entire life cycle, from production to disposal. This process involves gathering data on inputs, outputs, and emissions at each stage of a life cycle (Golsteijn, 2022). LCA software tools (e.g., SimaPro) are then used to model and assess these environmental impacts across multiple midpoint categories, such as greenhouse gas emissions, water use and eutrophication or endpoint categories such as human health, ecosystem quality and resource depletion (Jungbluth, 2024). Within the VCA4D framework, an LCA should present results in endpoint categories, also referred to as damage categories (Fabre et al., 2021). LCA provides several advantages. It allows the evaluation of different products, processes, or services regarding their environmental impacts and identifies critical processes that contribute to these impacts (Poratelli, 2022). However, LCA also has its disadvantages. It requires detailed and extensive data collection, and some environmental impacts might not be fully captured due to data limitations and modelling complexities (Chomkhamsri et al., 2012; Poratelli, 2022).

The economic analysis to answer FQ1 in the VCA4D framework involves calculating the GOP for the given year. While the Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) is another approach used in the literature (e.g., Kuwornu et al., 2018; Sain et al., 2017) for evaluating agri-food projects, it was not selected for this study. CBA typically involves quantifying the costs and benefits over a project's time frame (Szott & Motamed, 2024). This often includes calculations such as Net Present Value (NPV) or Internal Rate of Return (IRR) (Kuwornu et al., 2018; Sain et al., 2017). The reasons for using the GOP calculation instead of the CBA include several factors specific to the context of this research. First, the substrate is the primary investment difference between hydroponic and in-soil tomato cultivation in the region studied, which is currently an annual expense. Second, while greenhouses are long-term investments and could theoretically be analysed using CBA, this study focuses on annual costs because greenhouses can be used flexibly for different crops in subsequent years, not just to grow tomatoes. A CBA analysis

would not provide additional useful insights for this particular study. Thus, the VCA4D's annual picture of the GOP remains appropriate and ensures consistency with the environmental analysis. Moreover, the VCA4D includes broader economic impacts on the country's economy, such as the NPC and contribution to GDP, which are also crucial to answer RQ2.

Typically, in each field of the VCA4D research (economic, social, and environmental), specific experts conduct research within their respective areas and then synthesise their results. However, in this thesis, the approach is simplified and adapted to fit the scope of a master's thesis. The focus is set primarily on the economic and environmental aspects of the value chain. Detailed information on the methodology used in this thesis is presented in the subsequent chapter.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data collection

Throughout this study, data is gathered through expert interviews with corresponding farms and stakeholders from the Souss Massa region. To protect the privacy of the interviewees, we redact the names of the interviewees and their corresponding entities in this master's thesis. The questionnaire can be found in Appendix D.

Firstly, three hydroponic tomato producers in the region were interviewed. One farmer is a middle size producer with around 11 hectares of tomatoes, including the cultivation of round and cherry tomatoes. This producer is affiliated with a Moroccan cooperative. The other two farms cover 235 and 340 hectares, respectively, corresponding to large farms by national standards. One of the larger farms cultivates both round and cherry tomatoes, whereas the other is only producing cherry tomato varieties. The largest farm is operating using a closed-loop hydroponics system (explained in Chapter 4.1.2). On the middle sized farm, the interviewee was the producer, who is also the owner of the farm. On the largest farm, interviewee was the technical responsible who is an agronomist engineer. Lastly, on the third farm, the interviewee was the production manager.

To complete the value chain, we visited a local nursery and a commissioning station in the region. On these two sites, we were guided by the production manager and the quality responsible, respectively. This gave us the opportunity to ask additional questions to gather

information on production and processing. Moreover, we interviewed an experienced local agricultural consultant who provided a lot of contextual information. The last contact person is another experienced local farmer and entrepreneur. He provided us with additional insights into tomato production and the agricultural situation in Morocco. He is referred to in the text as *the local agricultural expert*.

The study includes both round tomatoes and cherry tomatoes. "Round tomatoes" refer to the standard loose tomatoes, while "cherry tomatoes" includes various small tomato varieties. Whenever tomatoes are mentioned in this thesis, all varieties are included.

3.2 Functional analysis (RQ1)

The functional analysis is based on a qualitative assessment of the conducted interviews. We gathered information on the different steps in the value chain, the actors involved, the structure, and the challenges faced in the tomato industry. We manually sort and evaluate the collected data according to its topic. The functional analysis includes all cited topics. The results are described and summarised to highlight the major findings and include:

- An overview of the value chain
- A description of the hydroponic cultivation techniques
- Contextual information about the value chain includes information on agriculture in Morocco, the structure and market dynamics of Moroccan tomato production, the supply season, subsidies, access to finances and, the societal context.

3.3 Economic analysis (RQ2)

3.3.1 Profitability of farm businesses

First, this section provides a qualitative description of the financial situation of farmers based on interviews. Second, expected expenses and revenues are calculated according to the information provided by the agricultural expert. This approach allows for an approximate quantitative comparison of the economic situations of different types of tomato cultivation. The cases examined are as follows:

- Case 1: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system
- Case 2: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, closed-loop system

- Case 3: Traditional tomato production in soil in Morocco
- Case 4: Hydroponic cherry tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system

For consistency, these cases are aligned to those used in the LCA. However, the calculations here are simplified, and no distinctions between the type of water and the energy source used are made. Therefore, for Cases 1 and 2, no distinction is made between a) and b).

The Value Added (VA) from farming is calculated using a simplified approach, primarily focusing on labour, management costs and financial charges. According to Fabre et al. (2021), a comprehensive VA calculation would also include land fees, royalties, insurances, and taxes on operations. These additional costs are not included because of a lack of detailed data, which may lead to an underestimation of the VA in the analysis. In this study, the VA for other value chain players, such as nurseries or commission agents, is not applicable. The VA is calculated according to the formula in Fabre et al. (2021), and is as follows:

$$VA = \text{labour Costs} + \text{management fees} + \text{financing costs} \quad (1)$$

In the context of the VCA4D, understanding the GOP is relevant for assessing the profitability of farm businesses. The GOP is calculated using the following formula:

$$GOP = \text{Revenue} - \text{Expenses} \quad (2)$$

The GOP is derived from the expected expenses and revenues based on information provided by the agricultural expert. The expenses include the greenhouse, substrate, seedlings, water, fertiliser, plant protection, labour costs, management fees, transport to the commissioning station, financing costs and extra costs (e.g., rope, bio stimulation). Additionally, for the closed-loop hydroponic the closed-loop installation is considered an expense. For the in soil cultivation instead of the substrate there are costs related to tillage and mulching. Appendix A provides detailed calculations for each expense and revenue. We convert the results into USD using the average currency exchange rate for the previous six months (06.12.2023–05.06.2024), which we retrieved from Investing.com (05.06.2024).

3.3.2 Total effects within the national economy

Contribution to Growth

To assess the contribution of the tomato value chain to the growth of the national economy, we consider statistics from the World Bank and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the

United Nations (FAO). These sources specifically provide data on the GDP of Morocco, the GDP attributable to the agricultural sector, the value of tomato production, and the value of vegetable production. With the provided numbers we determine the relative contribution of tomato production to the national GDP, to the agricultural sector GDP, and to the overall vegetable production. The statistics correspond to the year 2022. Both the World Bank and FAO use the average currency exchange rate of 2022, and the numbers are not adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP).

Income Distribution

First, export statistics from Moroccan tomato production are analysed to determine the total export amount and its value. By calculating the value of one kilogram of exported tomatoes and subtracting the producer price received per kilogram, the value generated outside the agricultural sector is determined. The commissioning costs are available from the interviews, which allows for the calculation of the remaining margin created in the value chain.

The farmer's share of the revenue generated from each kilogram of exported tomatoes is calculated as a percentage of the export revenue. Similarly, the commissioning station's share and the share of the remaining margin are calculated as percentages of the total export revenue.

3.3.3 Competitiveness in the international context

The NPC is calculated to assess international competitiveness. The NPC calculates the ratio of a product's domestic price to its international parity price. The formula is:

$$NPC = \frac{\textit{Domestic price of the product}}{\textit{International parity price of the product}} \quad (3)$$

Data on prices is sourced from online statistics (Numbeo, 2024). European statistics on tomato production (European Commission, 2024) provide additional insights into Morocco's role in the international market. These quantitative findings are further supported by qualitative information obtained from interviews.

3.4 Life Cycle Assessment (RQ3)

This thesis uses an LCA to analyse the environmental impacts of tomatoes. The LCA is carried out according to the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards (ISO 14040:2021-02). Following the ISO

standards, the LCA unfolds in four stages: Goal and Scope definition, Life Cycle Inventory Analysis, Impact Assessment and Interpretation.

3.4.1 Goal and scope definition

The following tomato cultivation options are considered in order to compare their environmental impact:

- Case 1: Hydroponic round tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system
 - o Case 1a: Irrigation: 100% well water, 100% electricity from the grid
 - o Case 1b: Irrigation: 60% well water and 40% desalinated water, 40% electricity from the grid and 60% renewable energy
- Case 2: Hydroponic round tomato production in Morocco, closed-loop system
 - o Case 1a: Irrigation: 100% well water, 100% electricity from the grid
 - o Case 1b: Irrigation: 60% well water and 40% desalinated water, 40% electricity from the grid and 60% renewable energy
- Case 3: Traditional round tomato production in soil in Morocco
- Case 4: Hydroponic cherry tomato production, open-loop system

The cases represent real scenarios described in Chapter 4.1. Case 1 includes an open-loop hydroponic system with two irrigation scenarios. Case 2 includes a closed-loop hydroponic system, as explained in Chapter 4.1.2, with the same irrigation scenarios a) and b) as in Case 1. The scenarios a) and b) are selected in order to get more details on the impact of differences in the agricultural phase. The main difference between the farms is the use of different water and electricity sources for irrigation. In this study, we refer to Case 3 as traditional tomato production, which involves growing tomatoes in soil. Case 4 is cherry tomato production in an open-loop hydroponic system. Although trivially both are tomatoes, round and cherry tomatoes do not necessarily fulfil the same purpose for a consumer. Thus, a comparison between the two products has to be done carefully. Nonetheless, it is crucial to estimate the environmental impact of cherry tomatoes next to round tomatoes since a shift in supply from round tomatoes to cherry tomatoes is observed (see Chapter 4.2.1). This study does not include different cultivation scenarios for cherry tomato production. Assumptions on the impact of the different cultivation systems can be made based on the results of round tomatoes.

We measure the environmental impact per kilogram of tomatoes produced at export gate (i.e., Functional Unit (FU) = 1 kilogram of tomatoes produced at export gate). Figure 1 illustrates the system model, which shows the system boundaries, including the agricultural phase (seedling and tomato production), the post-harvest processing phase and the distribution to export gate. International distribution, sale or disposal is not considered in this LCA. As a result, this entails estimations from cradle to export gate.

Figure 1: System boundary of the LCA

3.4.2 Life cycle inventory

For hydroponic round and cherry tomato production, we gather foreground inventory data through interviews with agricultural experts on three different farms. In addition, missing data was subsequently supplemented by enquiries to the local agricultural expert. Details on the interviewees can be taken from Chapter 3.1. For traditional tomato production, the study of Payen et al. (2015) is used as a reference where information on yield and fertiliser is withdrawn. The study analysed tomato production in soil in the same region in Morocco and was selected for that reason. Due to ongoing droughts (World Bank, 2023), the irrigation data for the traditional system is adjusted according to the estimation of the local agricultural expert, as the data in Payen et al. (2015) is valid for the time period from 2009 to 2011. Yield and fertiliser maximum values are considered from Payen et al. (2015). Data from the Ecoinvent database v3.10 is used to complement foreground inventory data. The data used are allocated according to the “cut-off approach”.

The functional analysis in Chapter 4.1 provides a detailed overview of the tomato value chain, as well as the hydroponic production systems and infrastructures in place in the region. Table 1 lists the key inventory data for the different cultivation cases. The detailed inventory including the calculations is available in Appendix B. The quoted numbers reflect the average experience of the farmers with the crop and represent average values for the region. Hydroponic round tomato production is linked to a yield of 250 tonnes per hectare per year. There is one cultivation season in a year which lasts 10.5 months. It includes 2.5 months of growth after plantation, followed by eight months of harvest. Regarding the substrate, one farmer used, as an exception in the season used, smaller substrate bags compared to the other two farms. Since this was an exception, the information on the weight and origin of the substrate bags is taken from the other two farms. For both farms, the origin of the substrate is India, and the weight accounts for 16 kilograms per bag. On one hectare, 3000 substrate bags are installed, with an average of four to five plants per bag. For all producers, the substrate is based on coco coir. The lifetime of a substrate is four years, however, due to the Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (ToBRFV) (see Chapter 4.1.2), raspberry farmers in the region use the substrate the remaining three years. In our study, one fourth of the substrate emissions are allocated to the tomato production.

Table 1: Overview of the key inventory data

Parameter	Unit	Case 1: Tomato, open- loop	Case 2: Tomato closed-loop	Case 3: Tomato, in soil	Case 4: Cherry tomato, open-loop
Yield	ton ha ⁻¹	250	250	234	150
Cycles per year		One	One	One	One
Substrate		Coco coir	Coco coir	Soil	Coco coir
Irrigation installation		Drip	Drip	Drip	Drip
Irrigation water	m ³ ha ⁻¹	7875	5513	9450	7875
Greenhouse structure		Canarian plastic greenhouse	Canarian plastic greenhouse	Canarian plastic greenhouse	Canarian plastic greenhouse
Fertilisation	kg N ha ⁻¹	1244.4	871.08	968	1244.4
	kg P2O5				
	ha ⁻¹	668.1	467.67	776	668.1
	kg K2O				
	ha ⁻¹	1224	856.8	2458	1224
Tillage		No	No	Yes	No
Packaging		Carton	Carton	Carton	Carton and Plastic
Transport to Europe		Refrigerated	Refrigerated	Refrigerated	Refrigerated
References		Interviews	Interviews	Payen et al. (2015); Interviews	Interviews

Farmers use seedlings from nurseries in the region. According to Google Maps, the average distance from nursery to farm is calculated. The weight of a tomato seedling transported including plastic pots and boxes for transport is used according to Stoessel et al. (2012). The farms have drip irrigation installed. The water usage varies between 20 and 30 litres per day per hectare: here, an average use of 25 litres is taken as a plausible value. The larger farms cover their water use partially, around 40%, with desalinated water from the desalination plant in Agadir, a coastal city in the Souss Massa region. The rest of the water is well water pumped from the ground with electricity. For one farmer, electricity is provided by the grid, while the other two farmers have solar panels installed. In the case of solar panels, they cover around 60% of their electricity demand. Table 2 provides an overview of the irrigation scenarios for case 1 and case 2.

Table 2: Irrigation scenarios for case 1 and case 2

Irrigation Input	Case 1a) and 2a)	Case 1b) and 2b)
Well water	100%	60%
Desalinated seawater	0%	40%
Electricity from the grid	100%	40%
Electricity from solar panels	0%	60%

The interviewees stated nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (NPK) as the most important fertiliser inputs. NPK input is estimated in this study using the information provided by the agricultural expert. No detailed number on pesticide use is available. Thus, the average pesticide input from Ecoinvent v3.10 is used for all cases. This number comes from tomato cultivation in Almeria, south of Spain. Work in the greenhouses is primarily done manually. On farm transport is considered according to Ecoinvent v3.10. Background data from Ecoinvent v3.10 is used to model the plastic greenhouse with steel bars. Greenhouse heating is not installed due to the moderate climate in the region all year around. One of the three farms had a closed-loop hydroponic system in place and reports water savings of around 30%. Because the recollected water is highly nutritious, it also saves inputs such as fertiliser. For simplicity, we assume the saved NPK input is also 30%. Grewal et al. (2011) suggest that this assumption is plausible and could potentially underestimate savings in N and K. This information is used to model the closed-loop system. In theory, the saved water and nutrients in the closed-loop system are being turned back into hydroponic tomato cultivation. Currently, due to ToBRFV (see Chapter 4.1.2) the water is given to neighbouring farmers not affected by the virus. However, our analysis of cases 1b) and 2b) assumes that these savings remain within the system, as is typically the case. Land transformation in the agricultural phase is accounted for according to Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023). It is important to note that the area in question is characterized by arid conditions with minimal vegetation, and no forests were cleared for agricultural purposes.

After harvest, the tomatoes are transported from the farm to the commissioning centre, in the surrounding neighbourhood. We use Google Maps to determine the average distance from the farm to the commissioning station. At the commissioning station, the tomatoes are brushed, washed, and dried. Afterwards, the tomatoes are electronically sorted. For estimating the water and electricity use, we rely on Stoessel et al. (2012) for the water consumed and Bosona and Gebresenbet (2018) regarding the electricity required for sorting and washing. Then, round tomatoes are packaged into cartons. We took the details on the weight of the cartons, in which

6 kilograms of tomatoes are packed, at the commissioning centre. Before dispatching, the tomatoes are stored overnight in a 4 to 6°C fridge. The next morning, tomatoes are shipped via lorry to Tangier. The distance from the commissioning station to Tangier was calculated using Google Maps. We model the transport using a lorry with refrigeration from Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023). Further transport to Europe is not within the system boundaries of this study. According to the interviewees, hydroponic cherry tomatoes use the same amount of input per hectare as round tomatoes but have a lower yield of 150 tonnes per hectare. That means cherry tomatoes use more input per FU compared to round tomatoes.

The average fertiliser content is calculated according to Kägi et al. (2021) and illustrated in Tables 3, 4 and 5. Emissions for Case 1, Case 3, and Case 4 are calculated according to Nemecek et al. (2023). We account for no emissions into the soil or groundwater in Case 2, the closed-loop hydroponic system, as no material flows out of the system. In consultation with the supervisor, we neglect emissions to the air due to the lower bacterial activity in the substrate compared to soil.

Table 3: Composition of average N-fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)

Substance	Urea	Ammonium Sulphate	Diammonium Phosphate	Ammonium nitrate phosphate	Monoammonium phosphate
Input (kg per kg N-Fertiliser)	0.236	0.058	0.025	0.645	0.009

Table 4: Composition of average P2O5-fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)

Substance	Triple Superphosphate	Single Superphosphate	Diammonium Phosphate	Ammonium nitrate phosphate
Input (kg per kg P2O5-Fertiliser)	0.411	0.044	0.261	0.285

Table 5: Composition of average K2O-fertiliser per kg (Kägi et al., 2021)

Substance	Potassium Chloride	Potassium Sulphate
Input (kg per kg K2O - Fertiliser)	0.884	0.117

3.4.3 Impact assessment

In this step, the life cycle inventory is assessed with regard to the impact on the environment. The impact analysis is calculated in two main steps. Firstly, substances from the life cycle inventory are sorted into classes regarding their impact on the environment. This step is called classification. That means for example, that both methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) have an effect on climate change, while emissions of sodium triphosphate (Na₅P₃O₁₀) lead to eutrophication of water bodies (Golsteijn, 2014). Secondly, in the characterisation the effect on the environment is calculated. That means that individual substances are multiplied by a factor according to their damage potential (Kägi et al., 2021). It evaluates, for example, the different impacts of CH₄ and CO₂ on climate change. Results can be illustrated via the midpoint or endpoint approach. Midpoint findings are expressed in units that are directly linked to pollution levels, such as CO₂ equivalents for climate change. The endpoint approach provides information about the harm to both humans and the environment. For instance, the harm to human life is quantified in terms of the number of years of life lost (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

In this study ReCiPe 2016 (Huijbregts et al., 2017) is used. This impact assessment method quantifies both midpoint and endpoint results. We chose this method due to its high scientific consistency (Jungbluth, 2024) and its accounting of endpoint indicators such as human health, ecosystem quality, and resource depletion, which are crucial in the assessment based on VCA4D (Fabre et al., 2021). Therefore, this master thesis primarily highlights the ReCiPe 2016 results at the endpoint level. Table 6 shows the three endpoint levels and the corresponding midpoint levels.

Additionally, to quantify the water footprint in the arid regions of Morocco we assess the AWARE method, developed by the Water Use in Life Cycle Assessment” (WULCA) working group of the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative (Boulay et al., 2018). Moreover, regarding the Global Warming Potential (GWP) ReCiPe 2016 is outdated since IPCC has defined newer characterisation factors (Jungbluth, 2024). Therefore, we also apply the IPCC 2021 GWP100 method separately (IPCC, 2023). Those two midpoint categories give a more comprehensive understanding of the impacts on the water footprint and climate change, two important indicators. The impact assessment is carried out with SimaPro software 9.5.

Table 6: Description of the endpoint levels including the corresponding midpoint levels (adjusted from Fabre et al. (2021) and Huijbregts et al., 2017)

Endpoint indicators: Damage to	Midpoint: Environmental problem	Aim at capturing	Usual indicator
Natural Resources	Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity	Depletion of resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-renewable: exhaustion of stocks • Renewable: rate of use higher than replacement 	Increased cost to continue extractions Unit= US \$
Ecosystem Quality	Climate Change, Photochemical ozone formation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Toxicity, Water consumption, Land use	Impairment in the functions and structure of natural ecosystems through a variety of damage to all kinds of local wildlife species leading to loss integrated over time	Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species (PDF) during one year Unit = species.yr
Human Health	Climate change, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionising radiation, Particulate matter formation, Photochemical ozone formation, Toxicity, Water consumption	Negative effects on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of life (morbidity) • Life expectancy (mortality) 	Disability Adjusted Loss of Life Years (DALY) Unit = DALY*

* Reduction of the potential number of healthy life years due to premature morbidity or mortality

4 Results

4.1 Functional analysis (RQ1)

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the hydroponic tomato value chain in Morocco. It begins with an examination of the various steps of the value chain, followed by a description of the hydroponic cultivation techniques used. Contextual information about the value chain is also presented.

4.1.1 Value chain overview

The tomato production process involves several stages, starting with agricultural production, which includes the cultivation of seedlings in local nurseries, on-farm production, and harvesting. This process is then followed by post-harvest treatment at the commissioning

station, and concludes with the distribution of tomatoes to various countries by lorry. These sequential steps are depicted in Figure 2 and further explained below.

Figure 2: Value chain overview

Farming Process

The farming process starts at local nurseries where tomato seedlings are cultivated. The process from seed to delivery of the seedling spans approximately 50 days, although this duration can vary slightly with seasonal changes, taking about 60 days during the colder winter months and reducing to 40 days in the summer. The stages include seeding, germination, grafting, and growing. Additionally, regular irrigation and fertilisation are critical throughout this phase to ensure healthy plant development.

Once the seedlings are mature, they are picked up or delivered to the farms. The tomatoes are then planted in coco coir substrates in metallic greenhouses. To protect against pests and environmental factors, the greenhouses are outfitted with plastic covers and side nets. Manual labour is predominantly used for plant handling and care. Farming activities include consistent irrigation, fertilisation, and plant protection measures. Greenhouse heating is not installed due to the moderate climate in the region all year around.

Approximately 2.5 months after planting, the first tomatoes are ready for harvest. The harvesting season then lasts for around 8 months. Harvesting is performed manually to ensure careful handling of the fruits.

Transport to commissioning station

Post-harvest, the logistics of tomato distribution depend on the size and structure of the farm. In some cases, cooperatives (e.g., Copag) are involved, while in other instances, vertically integrated supply chains manage the pickup and subsequent processes directly. To maintain freshness, the harvested tomatoes are transported to commissioning centres the same day they are picked. The temperature in the vehicle is set around 20°C, a crucial step to gently reduce the tomatoes' field temperature. Also at the centres, the tomatoes are initially stored at 20°C before further processing. They avoid direct cooling to 4 °C to avoid damaging the delicate fruits.

Cleaning and Sorting Process

The post-harvest processing of tomatoes begins with a cleaning process. Initially, the tomatoes are brushed to remove dirt or dust. Subsequently, they undergo a quick water wash before being dried. This process lasts only a few seconds. Following the cleaning, the tomatoes are conveyed through an advanced sorting system. The technology is designed to detect and remove tomatoes that do not meet the preset standards requested from the European retailer, such as incorrect sizes or visible defects like brown spots.

Packaging and Quality Control

Once sorted, the tomatoes undergo the packaging process. Round tomatoes are placed in larger cartons (i.e., around 6 kilogram), while cherry tomatoes are packed directly into smaller-sized plastic containers. Employees perform this task manually and visually carry out a secondary quality control check to ensure all packaged tomatoes meet the high-quality standards expected on the market.

Following packaging, they stack the cartons on pallets and put them into an overnight storage facility, maintaining temperatures between 4 and 6 °C. This step ensures freshness until shipment.

State Regulations and Controls

Before leaving the commissioning centre, each shipment must pass through two important state-imposed controls: normalisation and quality control. These controls are in place to maintain the high standards of exported Moroccan tomatoes and preserve their market reputation. A state

officer visits daily to oversee these checks and provides an authorization signature. If a shipment fails these tests, it is not allowed to leave the hub.

Transport and Distribution to Europe

The tomatoes are then transported to Europe primarily via refrigerated lorries that travel via Tangier. Some farms also use a ferry service from Agadir twice a week; however, this option is less frequent, although more cost-effective compared to lorry transport, which is almost twice as expensive. Once in Europe, the tomatoes are distributed across various countries, with France being the largest importer, followed by the United Kingdom. According to EU data, Morocco is the leading non-EU tomato producer for the European market, exporting 560,000 tonnes in 2022 and 500,000 tonnes in 2023. These figures highlight Morocco's role in the European tomato market, while other countries such as Turkey make a smaller contribution, exporting half of this volume to Europe (European Commission, 2024).

4.1.2 Tomato cultivation techniques

In the Souss-Massa region the cultivation of hydroponic tomatoes adapts to challenging environmental conditions, including poor soil quality and limited water resources. Hydroponics is a method of growing plants without soil, in which the roots are either in a mineral nutrient solution or in a substrate such as perlite or coconut fibres. Farmers in the region use substrate in their hydroponics cultivation. The installation is illustrated in Figure 3. Hydroponic systems can be categorised into open and closed systems, depending on their nutrient recycling. In open systems, surplus nutrient solutions are not recycled, leading to their disposal into the environment, whereas closed systems involve the collection and recycling of excess nutrients back into the system. Among the various substrates used in hydroponics, coconut fibres, also known as coco coir is the substrate used from the visited farms in this study. The substrate provides the essential characteristics for optimal plant growth, such as aeration

Figure 3: Hydroponic tomato cultivation in coco coir substrate

and nutrient retention. Derived from the fibrous husks of coconuts, coco coir is a by-product of the copra and fibre extraction industry. Prior to use, coco coir undergoes a composting process lasting 2-3 years, followed by dehydration and compression. Notably, coco coir exhibits chemical and physical properties similar to peat but with a higher pH and lower environmental impact, making it an increasingly favoured choice in soilless cultivation systems (Maucieri et al., 2019).

The implementation of drip irrigation, coupled with integrated infrared technology, facilitates real-time monitoring of substrate humidity levels, which allows precise and targeted water delivery directly to plant roots. This method not only optimises the moisture and nutrient intake of the plants but also reduces water usage compared to traditional farming methods (see Chapter 4.3). The same drip irrigation system applies fertilisers, directly nourishing the plant roots to enhance growth efficiency and crop yield. This system provides a controlled growing environment that consistently produces high-quality tomatoes.

Despite the advanced cultivation techniques in hydroponics, tomatoes are vulnerable to a variety of pests and diseases, which affect crop health and yield. The main health challenges currently affecting tomato crops in the region include the ToBRFV, whiteflies, and Tuta absoluta. ToBRFV is one of the most crucial. First identified in 2014 in Israel and shortly afterward in Jordan, ToBRFV has been persistent until today. The virus attacks tomato and pepper plants, causing symptoms such as mosaic-like discolorations on leaves and yellow spots on fruits. The virus affects the growth and financial viability of the plants leading to losses in harvest. ToBRFV is spread mechanically via direct contact with contaminated plants, humans, tools, soil, and water, and can also travel long distances through infected seeds and fruits (Agroscope, 2024). Currently, there is no effective pest management to fight ToBRFV once it has infected a crop (Bayer, n.d.-b). Given the absence of a definitive cure for ToBRFV, preventive hygiene from seed handling to harvest is crucial. The industry is searching for solutions to mitigate the effects of this virus. For instance, agricultural biotechnology firms such as Bayer, are developing and marketing crop varieties resistant to ToBRFV (Bayer, n.d.-a).

In the visited hydroponic greenhouses, preventive measures are necessary to protect against these threats, whereby the wearing of protective clothing such as blouses and possibly shoe covers, trouser protection and hairnets is mandatory. Additionally, hand disinfection is required when entering the greenhouses. This prevents the spread of diseases from external sources and

among different areas of the farm. The entrances to the greenhouses are equipped with angled plastic barriers designed to prevent insects from entering, an additional measure against external pest invasions.

4.1.3 Contextual information

Agriculture in Morocco

Despite the benefits of soilless cultivation methods and drip irrigation, which help reduce water consumption compared to traditional farming (see Chapter 4.3), water scarcity remains a significant challenge in Moroccan agriculture. This is particularly evident in the Souss Massa region, where the average yearly rainfall of 262 mm reminds us of desert conditions (El Hawari et al., 2023). The landscape reflects the arid climate, with sparse vegetation unless irrigation is implemented. Until today, farmers relied on accessible groundwater, extracted from depths varying between 120 and 260 meters, depending on proximity to the coast. While this method of irrigation has been cost-effective and convenient, current trends indicate a decline in groundwater levels, compounded by salinization and degradation. Factors such as high evaporation rates, limited groundwater recharge, intensive agriculture, and seawater intrusion lead to the salination and degradation process (Hssaisoune et al., 2020). These challenges not only raise environmental concerns but also lead to increased costs associated with groundwater drilling and issues regarding quality of water for agricultural use (see Chapter 4.2.1).

To address water scarcity, the Moroccan government initiated various desalination projects, including a facility in Agadir, a coastal city in the Souss Massa region, which has been operational since November 2022. The desalination plant works on reverse osmosis technology. Reverse osmosis is a technology that uses less energy compared to other desalination technologies (Raluy et al., 2006). A portion of the desalinated water is allocated for domestic drinking water, while the remaining portion is designated for agricultural use. Currently, the demand from farmers for desalinated water exceeds the available supply. Farmers were required to register their interest in desalinated water beforehand. However, we observed that only larger farms have been able to access this water resource. This access discrepancy can be attributed to a variety of factors. Firstly, smallholders (< 5 hectares) may not have been adequately informed about the registration process, or they may have found the bureaucratic procedures involved to be prohibitive. Additionally, it is possible that the lower interest from smallholders comes from

historically lower energy prices, which made groundwater pumping more economical compared to desalinated water. However, with rising energy costs, the price disparity between desalinated water and well water is diminishing. Nevertheless, well water remains a more cost-effective option for farmers at present (see Chapter 4.2.1). Moreover, among the farms visited, two use solar energy, while the third does not have solar panels installed. The representative from the latter farm stated that an installation is planned. The two farms with solar panels cover 40% of their irrigation energy needs with solar power, with the remaining 60% supplied by the electricity grid.

Structure and market dynamics

In the tomato cultivation sector of Souss Massa, there's a division between large-scale farms equipped with a vertically integrated supply chain owning operations from nurseries and farms to commissioning centres. On the other hand, small and medium-sized farms are organised individually or through cooperatives (e.g., Copag). In the region, there are numerous tomato producers, but there are fewer nurseries and commissioning stations. This structure implies that individual farmers have less bargaining power, as there is a higher level of competition between them compared to the competition between the nurseries and commissioning centres. Overall, commissioning stations have a significant influence on the whole value chain, serving as intermediaries between producers and the market. This role gives them considerable leverage, allowing them to determine product requirements and exert pressure on farmers to conform to market demands. In the export market to Europe, connections play a crucial role, with certification and product quality serving as additional determinants alongside price. Despite the structural dynamics, smallholders may face challenges in integrating into the value chain, often delivering products based on market demand fluctuations. This means that commissioning stations first favour the products of their own farms and then they take the products of smallholders in case they cannot supply the demand with their own production. This imbalance in power distribution underscores a certain vulnerability of smallholders within the system.

Supply season

In the tomato cultivation sector of Souss Massa, Morocco's competitive advantage lies in the production of tomatoes at lower costs during the winter months compared to Europe. Unlike most European production, the climate in the region allows the cultivation of tomatoes in winter

without heating infrastructure, making it more cost-effective (see Chapter 4.2). Moroccan farmers use this advantage and focus on winter supplies. However, to ensure a year-round income, tomato cultivation in Morocco persists throughout the year.

Our observations show that the cultivation cycles of farmers are similar, although not entirely identical. Generally, all producers engage in winter planting, with larger operations extending their production into the summer months, as mentioned above. The seasonal cycle can be outlined as follows:

- Winter plantation: Planting occurs from July to October, with harvesting starting after October and continuing until April. The peak harvest period typically falls in December and January.
- Summer plantation: Planting takes place from February to April, with harvesting spanning from April to December, reaching its peak in June.

It typically takes around 2.5 months from planting to the first harvest, with harvests lasting approximately 8 months. Notably, one of the farms visited has developed its own year-round supply strategy to meet market demands consistently.

Subsidies

In 2023, tomato producers in the region received a subsidy of 70,000 MAD per hectare to offset losses from the previous season's poor harvest, largely attributed to the ToBRFV. Despite the intention to foster exports by supporting production, our interviewees mentioned scientism among stakeholders regarding the effectiveness of this subsidy. They argued that instead of improving export competitiveness, the subsidy inadvertently led to an increase in supply, subsequently driving prices down in the winter of 2024. Interviewees proposed redirecting such financial support towards investments in infrastructure, like solar panels, to enhance long-term resilience and reduce dependency on seasonal subsidies. Before the introduction of the 70,000 MAD subsidy, different forms of support were available, such as financing for insect nets and land renovation. Notably, smaller landholders received full financing for renovation projects, while larger landowners received partial funding. In contrast to tomatoes, other vegetables like potatoes receive annual subsidies of 40,000 MAD per hectare, while support for crops like olives and oranges also exists. Additionally, drip irrigation systems are widely supported across the country.

Access to finances

Access to finances for farmers includes bank credits and government-sponsored programs like Forsa, Mobadara, and Intellaka, with low-interest rates and extended repayment periods. However, accessing credit requires a solid business plan. Furthermore, cooperatives play a role in providing affordable inputs to farmers by importing larger volumes without VAT, thus enabling them to offer lower prices.

The lives of locals

Public opinion regarding agricultural exports is divided, with concerns over the environmental impact and competition-driven price fluctuations. In fact, the export market's influence on local tomato prices can have different effects, potentially increasing competition and driving down prices due to heightened production, while simultaneously raising local prices through increased international demand. Furthermore, local communities frequently receive lower-quality production parts. The government's current focus on promoting exports contrasts with the desire of local communities for access to affordable, high-quality products themselves. Interviewees also highlight the issue of governmental support for imported products that could be produced domestically, such as fertilisers. This practice limits the country's opportunities for value creation. However, it is beyond the scope of the thesis to analyse the Moroccan government's international macroeconomic ambitions and policies and how they are in line with local food security.

4.2 Economic analysis (RQ2)

In this chapter, we first elaborate on the profitability of tomato production for farm businesses. Second, we show the effects within the national economy, and third, the competitiveness in the international context of tomato production.

4.2.1 Profitability of farm businesses

Hydroponic tomato production, while offering several agronomic benefits, involves higher initial investment costs compared to traditional soil-based methods. The major cost factor in the additional investment is the substrate bags for cultivation. At the same time, however, hydroponic farming reduces ongoing expenses related to key inputs such as fertiliser and water.

Closed-loop systems, which collect surplus water, realise further input savings. One farm with a closed system reported savings of up to 30% in water and fertiliser usage. However, such closed hydroponic systems are not yet widespread in the region studied. In my research, the largest farm of the three farms visited employed this technology. Presently, a challenge affecting these potential savings is ToBRFV, since the virus prevents the reuse of water due to the risk of disease transmission. As a result, the nutrient-rich water must instead be given to neighbouring farms growing crops not susceptible to the virus. The farmer mentioned that the water is provided to them free of charge. This cancels out the potential savings in water and fertiliser costs under the current conditions. For the substrate, there is a similar problem. Normally, substrates can be reused for up to four years. However, due to contamination risks from ToBRFV, substrates must now be replaced annually. The used substrate is sold to raspberry growers, who value it for its favorable pH value; this sale recovers around 40% of the original substrate costs. Yet, this increases annual expenses and operational complexity. The calculations in Table 7, assume for the closed-loop scenario (case 2) the reuse of the nutritious water, which usually would be the case. Furthermore, interviewees mention that recent external events like the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing war in Ukraine have impacted the economic environment for agriculture. They stated that since these events costs for inputs such as fertilisers and pesticides have risen, with increases of around 15% for fertilisers and 25% for pesticides. Furthermore, rising energy costs are affecting operations that require energy inputs, such as water pumping and irrigation.

Table 7 lists the relative agricultural expenses for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation. For the open-loop hydroponic system (case 1), the major cost drivers are the greenhouse and fertiliser, accounting for 20% and 17% of total agricultural costs, respectively. This is followed by seedlings, plant protection, and employment costs, each contributing around 12 to 16% of the total costs. In the closed-loop hydroponic system (case 2), fertiliser is not the primary cost driver, but it still accounts for 13% of the total costs. The greenhouse is the main cost driver at 21%, followed by employment at 17%, with seedlings and plant protection accounting for approximately 13% of the total costs. For traditional cultivation (case 3), the primary cost burdens are fertiliser, comprising around 25% of the total costs, and greenhouse at 20%. Seedlings, plant protection, and employment costs each contribute about 10 to 15%, similar to case 1. In cherry tomato production (case 4), seedlings are the main cost driver, accounting for 24% of the total costs, followed by employment costs at 18%.

Greenhouse maintenance, fertiliser, and plant protection each make up around 12 to 16% of the total costs. Notably, water for irrigation represents a small part of the total agricultural costs in all cases.

Table 7: Relative agricultural expenses for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation

Expenses	Case 1: Tomato, open- loop	Case 2: Tomato closed-loop	Case 3: Tomato, in soil	Case 4: Cherry tomato, open-loop
Canarian plastic greenhouse	20%	21%	20%	15%
Substrate	8%	8%	0%	6%
Seedlings	12%	13%	12%	24%
Water	3%	2%	3%	2%
Fertiliser	17%	13%	25%	13%
Plant protection	12%	12%	12%	13%
Employment costs	16%	17%	16%	18%
Management fees	3%	3%	3%	2%
Transport to commissioning station	2%	2%	1%	1%
Extra costs	2%	2%	0%	1%
Closed-loop installation	0%	2%	0%	0%
Estimated other costs traditional cultivation (Mulching, tillage, ...)	0%	0%	3%	0%
Financing costs	5%	5%	5%	5%

Note: All cost categories > 10% are coloured in red. In each category, the two highest categories are highlighted in darker red colour.

When analysing the value chain, including packaging and transport, agricultural production represents approximately 30 to 35% of the costs for cases 1 to 3. Packaging constitutes around 40%, and transport makes up about 30% of the total costs for these cases. For the cherry tomato production (case 4), agricultural costs account for approximately 45% of the total costs. Packaging contributes 35%, while transport makes up 20% of the total costs. Table 8 provides an overview of the relative expenses in the value chain for all cases.

Table 8: Relative expenses in the value chain for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation

Processes	Case 1: Tomato, open- loop	Case 2: Tomato closed-loop	Case 3: Tomato, in soil	Case 4: Cherry tomato, open-loop
Agricultural Production	33%	32%	35%	46%
Packaging	37%	38%	36%	36%
Transport	30%	30%	29%	18%

In Morocco, as highlighted in Chapter 4.1.3, water is a critical limiting resource. Historically, farmers have relied on the accessible and economically viable option of groundwater for irrigation. Until today, this method has not presented major disadvantages and has remained cost-effective. The analysis shows that irrigation only contributes to a small part of the total costs. However, recent developments indicate that groundwater levels are dropping, with increasing salinization and degradation being observed (El-Ghzizel et al., 2021). This environmental degradation not only raises ecological concerns but also raises operational costs for farmers due to the need for deeper drilling. Moreover, beyond a depth of approximately 200 meters, the water quality deteriorates significantly, becoming too saline for agricultural use. Faced with these challenges, farmers are looking for alternative water sources. One option is desalinated seawater. In Agadir, a coastal city in the Souss Massa region, Morocco hosts a desalination plant. Despite this facility, the demand for desalinated water currently exceeds its supply, with access largely limited to larger farms (see Chapter 4.1.3). The cost of desalinated water is at MAD 10 per cubic meter, of which half is subsidised by the state, leaving farmers to pay the remaining MAD 5 per cubic meter. In comparison, groundwater costs only around MAD 2 per cubic meter, making it a more cost-effective option in the short term. Yet, the ongoing depletion and increasing salinity of groundwater, compounded by rising energy costs for pumping, are making this resource long-term less sustainable and more expensive.

Table 9: GOP for the four cases of tomato production

	Unit	Case 1: Tomato, open-loop	Case 2: Tomato closed-loop	Case 3: Tomato, in soil	Case 4: Cherry tomato, open-loop
Yield	kg/ha	250'000	250'000	234'000	150'000
Total costs per hectare	MAD/ha	562'328	537'075	567'904	761'696
Total Revenue per hectare	MAD/ha	683'750	683'750	639'990	945'000
GOP per hectare	MAD/ha	121'423	146'675	72'086	183'304
GOP in \$ per hectare	USD/ha	12'142	14'668	7'209	18'330

In the context of the VCA4D, understanding the GOP and the VA is relevant for assessing the profitability of the farm business. The analysis shows a positive GOP for the average producer price received in 2022 for all cases (see Table 9 and Appendix A). However, the analysis indicates that open-loop hydroponics (case 1), compared to traditional cultivation (case 3), generates approximately 40% more profit. Lower fertiliser input, lower water costs, and a higher yield per hectare balance out the investment costs in the substrate. In a closed-loop

hydroponic system (case 2), additional savings are realised, resulting in around 20% more profit compared to the open-loop hydroponic system (case 1), due to further reductions in water and fertiliser usage. According to the analysis, cherry tomatoes (case 4) are 50% more profitable compared to closed-loop hydroponic round tomatoes (case 1). VA per hectare is estimated at around MAD 135'000 (USD 13'500) per hectare for round tomatoes and MAD 190'000 (USD 19'000) for cherry tomatoes, likely underestimated since other factors as described in Fabre et al. (2021) are not considered in the analysis.

In the region examined, farmers generally cultivate both cherry and round tomatoes, but a shift towards exclusively growing cherry tomatoes is notable among the farms visited. Specifically, one out of three farms focused solely on cherry tomato varieties, and one of the other farmers plans to switch to only growing cherry tomatoes in the upcoming season. This shift is driven by the economic dynamics of tomato production; the farmers highlighted that the price pressures on round tomatoes can be so severe that their production sometimes becomes unprofitable. Although cherry tomatoes have lower productivity and higher demands on labour and inputs per kilogram produced compared to round tomatoes, their increased market price makes them more profitable. This makes the cultivation of cherry tomatoes a strategic economic decision as the analysis shows. Appendix A details specific expenses per hectare of tomato production, offering an overview of the total cost implications for hydroponic open- and closed-loop, soil-based and cherry tomato cultivation.

4.2.2 Total effects within the national economy

Contribution to growth

In 2022, Morocco's overall GDP was reported to be MAD 1'330 billion (USD 130.91 billion) (World Bank, 2023), with the agricultural sector contributing approximately 9.7% to the national economy, equivalent to an estimated MAD 129'661 million (USD 12'761.048 million). The country produced 1'388'542 tonnes of tomatoes, with an average producer price of USD 3050 per tonne, culminating in an estimated market value of MAD 4'235'053 million (USD 416'809 million) in 2022. Within the agricultural sector, that implies that tomato production contributes about 3.3% to the total agricultural value produced. Moroccan tomato production contributes roughly 0.3% of the overall GDP. In particular, tomatoes represent about 32.1% of the GDP generated from vegetable production. In Morocco's agricultural sector,

tomatoes, potatoes, and apples account for the majority of value creation, following olives and wheat. These statistics are derived from data provided by the Food and Agriculture Organization's databank and include all sorts of tomatoes (FAO, 2024)

Income Distribution

In 2022, Morocco exported 80% of its tomato production overseas, which corresponds to 740'660.97 tonnes. The total revenue generated from those exports amounted to approximately MAD 10'410'537 million (USD 1'024'593 million). This translates to an average income of MAD 14.1 (USD 1.38) per kilogram of export. FAO statistics report an average producer price of MAD 3.05 (FAO, 2024). Considering the entire value chain, the agricultural sector generates MAD 11.05 per kilogram of tomato. Our research shows that the costs associated with commissioning are about MAD 4.45 per kilogram. Thus, the remaining margin after deducting the costs for commissioning from the value generated outside the agricultural sector is MAD 6.60.

That means the farmer's share of the revenue generated from each kilogram of tomatoes exported, when calculated as a percentage of the export revenue, is 25%. The commissioning station's share is 32%. Various other entities involved in the value chain, such as traders, presumably split the remaining 44%.

4.2.3 Competitiveness in the international context

The NPC provides insights into Moroccan tomato production's competitiveness in the international context. The NPC is calculated by dividing the product's domestic price by its international parity price. For Moroccan tomatoes, the NPC is calculated as follows:

$$NPC = \frac{0.71^1 \text{ USD/kg}}{2.61 \text{ USD/kg}} = 0.27 \tag{4}$$

The NPC value below 1 indicates that the domestic value is lower than the international market price, suggesting that the overall value chain remuneration is lower than it would be if priced at international parity. This can be interpreted as a competitive advantage in the global market because it implies that Morocco's production cost allows for the sale of tomatoes at a lower

¹ (Numbeo, 2024)

price while still maintaining market presence. On the global tomato market, Morocco is in fact the third largest exporter of tomatoes after Mexico and the Netherlands. In 2022 Morocco surpassed Spain, traditionally a major producer, moving Spain to the fourth position (European Commission, 2024).

Morocco's competitive advantage in tomato production is explained by two main factors. On one hand, the labour costs are relatively low. For instance, in Spanish tomato production, as shown in Torrellas et al. (2012), labour accounts for around 60% of the total costs, whereas our results show labour costs around 15 to 20% of the total costs. On the other hand, it is the climatic advantage that provides an environment that is ideal for tomato cultivation. In the region, there is no need for greenhouse heating or cooling infrastructure year round. This advantage allows Moroccan farmers to operate with lower production costs during the winter months compared to their European counterparts, such as the Netherlands, where heating greenhouses is necessary during the winter (Torrellas et al., 2012).

Although the value chain remuneration is lower than under the international parity price, access to international markets provides Moroccan farmers with opportunities to earn higher revenues compared to selling locally, where prices are lower. Hydroponic production, which yields higher quality tomatoes, is especially well-suited for these export opportunities. However, integration into the global market also exposes farmers to the volatility of prices, which fluctuate in response to events such as changes in supply and demand, weather conditions, pests, diseases, and strategic agricultural decisions at both local and international levels. Interviewees highlighted the unpredictability of prices and their high variability, noting that during periods of very low prices, the costs associated with packaging and transport can exceed the selling price, making exports economically unviable. In such scenarios, tomatoes are diverted to the local market, which increases local supply and consequently drives prices down. While this situation benefits local consumers by making tomatoes more affordable, it adversely affects farmers' incomes. Interviewees pointed out that, next to water scarcity, the main challenge for them is market volatility. They mentioned that round tomato prices in recent years have fluctuated between MAD 1.5 per kilogram and MAD 10 per kilogram. The extreme price of MAD 10 per kilogram in 2023 was an outlier, driven by an acute supply shortage. Farmers mentioned that price pressure on cherry tomatoes is less severe compared to round tomatoes.

4.3 Life cycle impact assessment (RQ3)

The presentation of the LCA results begins with an overview of findings from ReCiPe 2016, focusing on endpoint level results. Cases 1 to 4 are analysed to determine their environmental impact. Additionally, we identify the contributions of different phases and processes in the value chain. Following this, the results from IPCC 2021 are presented. Lastly, the findings from AWARE are illustrated to offer further understanding of the water footprint.

4.3.1 ReCiPe

Among the analysed cases, the lowest environmental footprint on the damage to ecosystems is observed in case 2b, the closed-loop hydroponic system utilising 40% desalinated water and 60% solar energy for irrigation. Closed-loop hydroponics (case 2a and 2b) outperforms open-loop hydroponics (case 1a and 1b) and traditional cultivation (case 3) by approximately 20%. The latter (case 3) exhibits a comparable environmental impact to the open-loop hydroponic (case 1a and 1b), with a slightly lower impact than the open-loop without desalinated seawater and solar energy (case 1a) by 5% and a slightly higher impact than the open-loop with desalinated water and solar energy (case 1b) by 1%. Moreover, the transition to 40% desalinated seawater in hydroponic scenarios 1b and 2b compared to 1a and 2a without desalinated seawater yields a positive impact on ecosystems due to reduced water consumption, resulting in a 6% improvement in the open-loop (case 1) and 5% in the closed-loop (case 2).

Table 10: Total damage of each case to each damage (=endpoint) category

Damage category	Unit	Case 1a, open-loop	Case 1b, open-loop	Case 2a, closed-loop	Case 2b, closed-loop	Case 3, in soil	Case 4a, cherry
Human health	DALY	1.04E-06	1.03E-06	8.93E-07	8.88E-07	9.89E-07	1.60E-06
Ecosystems	species.yr	4.33E-09	4.08E-09	3.42E-09	3.25E-09	4.13E-09	6.34E-09
Resources	USD2013	3.21E-02	3.20E-02	3.14E-02	3.14E-02	3.12E-02	4.25E-02

In terms of human health, closed-loop hydroponics (case 2a and 2b) emerges as the most favourable performer. The damage to human health is about 10 to 14% lower than in the open-loop scenario (case 1a and 1b) and traditional cultivation (case 3). Case 3 presents a comparable impact on human health as Case 1 (a and b), with deviations of 4 to 5%. With or without the use of desalinated seawater and solar energy, scenarios a) and b) in open- and closed-loop hydroponics (cases 1 and 2) have similar impacts on human health. Although solar energy has

a positive impact on human health as the analysis in Appendix C.1 shows, the overall system's effect is marginal, resulting in a reduction in the impact on human health by less than 1%.

Regarding resource depletion, the hydroponic open- and closed-loop and the traditional cases (cases 1, 2, and 3) manifest a comparable impact, with the open-loop (case 1) and the traditional cultivation (case 3) deviating by approximately +/-1% from the closed-loop (case 2), indicating no significant variation.

Despite utilising the same cultivation technique as open-loop hydroponic round tomato production (case 1), case 4 involves the production of cherry tomatoes instead of round tomatoes. Cherry tomatoes exhibit the highest environmental impact across all categories. The analysis indicates that cherry tomatoes have a higher impact per FU compared to round tomatoes, particularly evident in the higher impact on human health and ecosystem quality by around 50% and by around 30% on resources, respectively. No alternative cultivation scenarios for cherry tomatoes are explored in this study. Figure 4 illustrates the relative contribution of each case compared to the case with the highest impact in each endpoint category. Table 10 presents the absolute impacts.

Figure 4: Relative contribution of each case compared to the case with the highest impact to each damage (=endpoint) category

At the midpoint level, the closed-loop hydroponic system (case 2a and b) presents substantially lower impacts on stratospheric ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, and water consumption compared to the other cases.

Conversely, cherry tomatoes (case 4) exhibit the highest environmental impact across all midpoint categories. Appendix C.2 provides detailed absolute figures at the midpoint levels, along with the relative contributions.

Figure 5: Relative contribution of the value chain steps to each damage category

Examining the process contribution to the overall damage, the agricultural phase exhibits the highest environmental impact on ecosystems and human health for all cases. Figure 5 displays the relative contribution of the value chain steps to each damage category. The agricultural phase includes processes highlighted in turquoise. Various factors contribute to this result, notably greenhouse construction, which alone accounts for over 35% of the overall contribution to damage to human health in all cases, and approximately 20% for resource depletion. Additionally, agricultural production (including emissions from fertilisers and pesticide application, seedling production, on farm transport, land transformation and tillage if applicable) significantly impacts ecosystem quality, contributing to more than 20% of damage, and over 10% of damage to human health in cases 1, 3, and 4. Notably, the closed-loop hydroponic system (case 2), substantially reduces the impact of agricultural production on ecosystems by almost 70% compared to the open-loop system, (case 1), while also decreasing the impact on human health by around 95%. Irrigation and substrate usage contribute approximately 10 to 15% to the overall damage in hydroponic cases 1, 2, and 4, while irrigation has a higher impact on ecosystems, reaching 20% in traditional cultivation (case 3). However, substrate emissions equal zero in the production in soil (case 3), where no substrate is used. Upstream processes, particularly fertiliser and pesticide purchases, contribute less than 10% to all three damage categories.

In the post-harvest processing stage, packaging contributes approximately 10% of damage to human health and resource depletion and around 20 to 30% of damage to ecosystem quality in all cases. Cleaning and sorting have a minor impact, accounting for less than 5% of the overall impact across the three damage categories in all cases. Following greenhouse construction, transport emerges as the second-largest contributor to damage to human health, with approximately 20 to 25% of the total impact. On resource depletion, transport has the highest contribution, accounting for 50% of the total damage in cases 1 to 3. On ecosystems, transport has an impact of around 15%. However, in cherry tomato production (case 4), where the agricultural phase dominates the impact, transport accounts for a smaller proportion. Table 11 details the absolute numbers for all cases, while Figure 5 illustrates the relative contributions.

Table 11: Absolute contribution of the value chain steps to each damage category

End-point	Case	Agricultural Phase					Post-harvest processing		Transport
		Agri-cultural Produc-tion	Green-house	Fertiliser and Pesticides	Substrate	Irrigation	Process-ing	Packag-ing	Distribu-tion
Eco-systems	Open-loop	1.04E-09	3.85E-10	1.31E-10	4.93E-10	6.46E-10	7.49E-11	9.99E-10	5.65E-10
	Closed-loop	3.30E-10	3.85E-10	1.25E-10	4.93E-10	4.52E-10	7.49E-11	9.99E-10	5.65E-10
	In soil	1.10E-09	4.12E-10	1.56E-10	0.00E+00	8.29E-10	7.49E-11	9.99E-10	5.65E-10
	Cherry	1.72E-09	6.42E-10	2.81E-10	8.21E-10	1.08E-09	7.49E-11	1.15E-09	5.65E-10
Human health	Open-loop	1.38E-07	3.64E-07	6.79E-08	7.69E-08	3.43E-08	3.64E-08	8.69E-08	2.33E-07
	Closed-loop	4.29E-09	3.64E-07	6.71E-08	7.69E-08	2.40E-08	3.64E-08	8.69E-08	2.33E-07
	In soil	1.17E-07	3.89E-07	8.24E-08	0.00E+00	4.40E-08	3.64E-08	8.69E-08	2.33E-07
	Cherry	2.28E-07	6.07E-07	1.51E-07	1.28E-07	5.72E-08	3.64E-08	1.59E-07	2.33E-07
Res-ources	Open-loop	6.53E-05	6.47E-03	2.48E-03	1.76E-03	7.90E-04	1.63E-03	3.37E-03	1.55E-02
	Closed-loop	6.53E-05	6.47E-03	2.11E-03	1.76E-03	5.53E-04	1.63E-03	3.37E-03	1.55E-02
	In soil	1.28E-04	6.91E-03	2.69E-03	0.00E+00	1.01E-03	1.63E-03	3.37E-03	1.55E-02
	Cherry	4.94E-05	1.08E-02	4.70E-03	2.93E-03	1.32E-03	1.63E-03	5.57E-03	1.55E-02

In summary, hotspots in terms of damage to ecosystems are agricultural production (with the exception of the closed-loop scenario) and packaging. The damage of agricultural production comes from the application of NPK fertilisation, while the damage of packaging comes from the land use required for carton production (see Appendix C.3). Regarding human health, greenhouse construction, followed by transport are significant contributors. The damage from greenhouse construction to human health is complex, but likely due to the manufacturing process (Payen et al., 2015). The damage from transport originates from the combustion of

fossil fuels which impacts GWP and ozone formation (see Appendix C.3). A sensitivity analysis shows that the high contribution of transport to the total impact is not mainly attributable to cooling (see Appendix C.4). Lastly, for resource depletion, transport followed by greenhouse construction are the primary contributors. The resource depletion impact from transport and greenhouse construction is driven by the extraction of non-renewable resources such as fossil fuels and steel (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

4.3.2 IPCC 2021

Figure 6: Relative contribution of each case to GWP 100

Applying the IPCC 2021 GWP 100, the various cultivation methods show similar impacts on GWP. Figure 6 provides an overview of the relative contribution to GWP of each case compared to the case with the highest GWP. The closed-loop hydroponic (case 1) exhibits 0.28 kilograms of CO₂ equivalent, the closed-loop (case 2) records 0.26 kilogram of CO₂ equivalent, and the traditional cultivation (case 3) shows 0.27 kilograms of CO₂ equivalent per FU. Beyond that, cherry tomato production (case 4) displays a higher GWP of 0.39 kilograms of CO₂ equivalent per FU. According to the analysis in Appendix C.5, employing 100% solar energy for irrigation results in a 30% reduction in CO₂ equivalent emissions compared to the irrigation scenario without solar energy. However, this does not influence the overall result. Notably, desalinated water from reverse osmosis has no visible impact on GWP, which is likely due to the efficient use of energy in osmosis plants (Raluy et al., 2006). Consequently, the impact of solar energy adoption and desalinated water usage in hydroponic scenarios 1b and 2b does not reflect in Figure 6.

4.3.3 AWARE

Figure 7: Relative contribution of each case to the water footprint

Figure 7 gives an overview of the relative contribution to the water footprint of each case compared to the case with the highest water footprint. Regarding the water footprint the hydroponic system shows an overall lower impact. First, the open-loop (case 1a) shows a 21% lower footprint than the cultivation in soil (case 3). Secondly, case 2a, the closed-loop system, reduces the impact by 44% compared to cultivation in soil (case 3). In addition, the use of 40% desalinated seawater and 60% well water instead of 100% well water reduces the footprint again for both cases 1b and 2b. Case 1b, compared to 1a, and Case 2a, compared to 2b, respectively, reduce the footprint by 42%. Cherry tomatoes have the highest water footprint per kilogram produced. In numbers, 66% more than round tomatoes – both hydroponically (open-loop) produced. Table 12 provides absolute numbers on the water footprint.

Table 12: Absolute water footprint of all the cases

Impact category	Unit	Case 1a, open-loop	Case 1b, open-loop	Case 2a, closed-loop	Case 2b, closed-loop	Case 3, in soil	Case 4, cherry
Water use	m ³	2.59	1.49	1.85	1.08	3.29	4.31

To conclude, my findings based on ReCipe 2016 suggest that the closed-loop system exhibits the lowest environmental impact, with further potential for reduction through the integration of desalinated water. Conversely, an open-loop hydroponic system does not have a lower environmental impact than traditional cultivation methods, except for the water footprint, where AWARE analysis indicates improvements. Notably, cherry tomatoes stand out with the highest impact across all damage categories, attributed to lower productivity and higher inputs per FU compared to other cases.

5 Discussion

5.1 Synthesis of the results

Agriculture in Morocco significantly contributes to the country's GDP, accounting for approximately 10%, in contrast to the EU average of 1.8% (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2022). Within this sector, vegetable production, particularly tomatoes, plays a central role. Sous Massa, the region studied, is notably the primary area for agricultural production aimed at export (Ministère de l'Agriculture, de la Pêche Maritime, du Développement Rural et des Eaux et Forêts, n.d.). The study shows that hydroponic tomato production in Morocco is part of a well-organised and structured value chain that integrates into the European tomato market. Notably, 80% of the tomatoes produced in Morocco are exported overseas (FAO, 2024), with Morocco being the main non-EU supplier to the EU (European Commission, 2024). We find that Moroccan farmers focus primarily on winter cultivation and use their climatic advantage to produce tomatoes without heating. This results in lower production costs compared to their European counterparts, such as those in the Netherlands, where greenhouse heating is necessary during the winter months (Torrellas et al., 2012).

The economic analysis in this study reveals business profitability for Moroccan farmers based on the average producer price. Although hydroponic systems require higher investments compared to traditional cultivation, primarily due to the (currently annual) cost of substrates, these are offset by lower fertiliser inputs, reduced water costs, and higher yields per hectare. Souza et al. (2019) support that finding and conclude that hydroponics ensures the financial viability of investments, making it an attractive food production solution.

The major cost components for the farmers in our study are greenhouses, fertilisers, seedlings, labour costs, and plant protection. Each expense contributes roughly 10 to 25% of the total costs. Compared to Torrellas et al. (2012), the absolute costs and revenue per square meter in Morocco are lower than in Spain, where labour represents 60% of total costs. Similarly, Testa et al. (2014) find higher costs per square meter for greenhouses in Italy, with labour being the main cost driver at 40% of total costs. Similar to the present study, Testa et al. (2014) identify greenhouses, fertilisers, and seedlings as significant cost factors. And Torrellas et al. (2012) name fertilisers, substrate, electricity, and greenhouse structure as significant cost factors. Testa et al. (2014) find minimal profits for Italian farmers, with a return of only € 0.01€ per kilogram,

which is remarkably lower than the profits observed in our study in Morocco. The Italian study focused on small-sized farms, which according to them have low bargaining power and high production costs due to unproductivity (Testa et al., 2014). In contrast, the present study in Morocco surveyed medium and larger farms, which are likely to higher bargaining power and may benefit from economies of scale. However, my interviewees also noted, that smallholders in Morocco are the most vulnerable in the system.

Overall, we find that Morocco's low labour costs and favourable climatic conditions make it highly competitive internationally. Morocco is the third-largest exporter of tomatoes after Mexico and the Netherlands (European Commission, 2024). Among the different cultivation methods, our study finds that cherry tomatoes yield the highest profitability for farmers, followed by closed-loop, open-loop, and traditional cultivation systems. In particular, farmers experience less market pressure on the price of cherry tomatoes. We can argue that the lower market pressure could be a result of higher demand compared to supply. Furthermore, cherry tomatoes have a higher value added. However, if a significant number of farmers transition to exclusively producing cherry tomatoes, the resultant increase in supply could lead to a decrease in market prices and subsequently diminish profitability. Therefore, a monoculture strategy focusing solely on the production of cherry tomatoes poses economic risks.

Considering environmental sustainability, hydroponic open-loop systems have impacts similar to traditional cultivation systems. However, they reduce water use on the farms, which is crucial for Morocco's arid regions. This lower water footprint is also supported by studies from Ntinis et al. (2017) and Alshrouf (2017). Furthermore, the closed-loop hydroponic system performs best across all environmental damage categories (ecosystems, human health, and resource depletion), which is in line with findings from Gartmann et al. (2023), Massa et al. (2010), and D'Amico et al. (2023). This system prevents fertilisers and pesticides from entering the soil, reducing emissions, and retaining nutrients within the system. Grewal et al. (2011), as in the present study, indicate a 30% reduction in water usage through recycling drainage water. Moreover, they also highlight the high potential for nutrient recovery. However, closed-loop systems face additional challenges, such as the increased vulnerability to pests and disease transmission, with ToBRFV currently a major concern. A suitable recycling process for drainage water, which was not closely studied here, could potentially solve the issue.

A seawater desalination plant in Agadir helps to mitigate water scarcity in the Souss Massa region and improve the water footprint without negatively impacting GWP. The impact of desalination plants on GWP is a concern in the literature (Martin-Gorriz et al., 2021), however, in this case the negative impact on GWP is likely to be reduced by the use of the energy-efficient reverse osmosis technology in the desalination plant in Agadir (Raluy et al., 2006). Besides the energy concerns of desalination plants, another concern is the negative impact on marine ecosystems. This impact is primarily driven by the disposal of the waste created during the reverse osmosis system (i.e., the brine) (Xu et al., 2013). A detailed analysis of brine disposal from the desalination plant in Agadir is beyond the scope of this thesis. However, to assess the environmental impact of the desalination, ecoinvent v3.10 (2023) background data was used. This data is based on global averages for reverse osmosis systems and includes disposal and emissions to water in the assessment. Overall, our analysis indicates that using desalinated seawater results in less damage to ecosystems compared to using groundwater, although only to a small extent. According to the results, we assume that the negative impact of groundwater use on ecosystems is greater than that of desalinated seawater. Nonetheless, the literature indicates that advancements are still required to make desalination a sustainable solution for meeting global freshwater demands (Darre & Toor, 2018).

Moreover, rebound effect is another issue. While hydroponics improves water efficiency, the positive effects may be negated if many more farmers engage in tomato production. This can lead to increased overall water usage. Additionally, the total negative impact on the environment may increase as more farmers engage in hydroponic open-loop production. It presents a dual challenge: while tomato production generates crucial income for local farmers and contributes substantially to the national economy, it also increases the environmental impact and competition for locally available resources.

High energy use in hydroponics is a growing concern (Gołasa et al., 2021; Mahdavian & Wattanapongsakorn, 2017). As a result, we investigated the installation of solar energy for irrigation, which had no significant impact on IPCC metrics. Although, studies suggest that renewable energy sources can substantially improve the carbon footprint of hydroponics (Chel & Kaushik, 2011; Gorjian et al., 2021; Ntinis et al., 2017). In Morocco, however, no lighting or greenhouse heating is needed, which reduces the overall energy demand and can partially explain the low impact of solar energy in the study region. The GWP of Moroccan hydroponic systems is comparable to the figures found by Torrellas et al. (2012) and Martin-Gorriz et al.

(2021), although they only analysed the LCA up to the farm gate. This suggests that the agricultural phase in Morocco has a smaller GWP impact compared to the stated studies. The results from the two cited studies in unheated greenhouses (Martin-Gorriz et al., 2021; Torrellas et al., 2012), as well as our study, are significantly lower than the GWP values stated by Boulard et al. (2011) and Torrellas et al. (2012) for heated greenhouses.

The ReCiPe analysis identifies agricultural production (i.e., emissions from fertilisers and pesticide application, seedling production, on farm transport, land transformation and tillage if applicable) and packaging as hotspots for ecosystem damage, with closed-loop systems notably reducing the impact of intensive agriculture. For damage to human health, greenhouse construction and transport are important contributors, while resource depletion is primarily driven by transport and greenhouse construction, in line to findings by Payen et al. (2015). These environmental findings align partially with the economic analysis. While the total agricultural impact on the environment is higher than reflected in the costs, within the agricultural phase the same hotspots are identified. The economic analysis reveals greenhouses, fertilisers, and crop protection as the primary cost factors, which is mirrored in the environmental impact of agricultural production and greenhouse structure. Furthermore, the closed-loop system reduces fertiliser input costs, which is also reflected in environmental benefits. Throughout the value chain, packaging and transport are important cost factors that align with their negative environmental impacts. In contrast, seedlings, while being an important cost factor, have a relatively low environmental impact. Water scarcity, although a significant problem in the region, irrigation does not prominently stand out as a high cost factor or an environmental burden according to ReCiPe.

Results indicate that cherry tomatoes generate the best income for farmers, add the highest economic value to the country, but have the highest environmental impact per kilogram due to higher input usage per FU compared to round tomatoes. However, one must be careful when comparing round tomatoes and cherry tomatoes. While both are tomatoes, they are not identical varieties. The present study does not assess different cultivation methods for cherry tomatoes to compare their environmental footprints. Nevertheless, we assume that closed-loop systems can also significantly improve the environmental footprint of cherry tomato production, as is the case with round tomatoes.

The adoption of hydroponics addresses the water challenge and, in closed-loop systems, also mitigates the issue of NPK leakage into the soil. However, other challenges persist or new ones emerge. For instance, the hydroponic tomato cultivation systems in this study are all monoculture. Due to the genetic properties of tomatoes, they are highly susceptible to various pests and diseases (Panno et al., 2021) and monoculture cultivation exacerbates this vulnerability (Uddin et al., 2014). This enhances the use of pesticides. Additionally, there is an ongoing dependence on synthetic fertilisers, which pose environmental concerns not only due to their potential to leach into the soil but also for instance because of the energy-intensive production of nitrogen (Walling & Vaneeckhaute, 2020) or the mining of phosphate (Yang et al., 2014). Furthermore, rebound effects may occur, negating some of the anticipated benefits as discussed above.

Furthermore, our analysis suggests that the environmental impact of materials used for greenhouse structures, which are integral to hydroponic systems, should not be overlooked, as they are a major burden on human health. This implies that if we plan to expand hydroponic farming, the negative impact of materials used for greenhouse structures (e.g., steel and plastic) will increase. Our study shows that the total agricultural phase (including greenhouse structure among others) has the greatest impact on ecosystems and human health. However, a detailed comparison of the processes within the three phases shows that transport also causes a relatively important damage to human health and resource depletion. Literature often compares local production with greenhouse heating to long-distance production without greenhouse heating, finding that transport is a lower burden than heating the greenhouse (Payen et al., 2015; Urbano et al., 2022). Nonetheless, our study shows that the impact of transport should not be underestimated, particularly since our system boundary does not yet include further distribution in Europe.

5.2 Recommendations

Hydroponic installations improve water footprints and have the potential to increase incomes compared to traditional tomato cultivation due to higher productivity in the controlled system. Closed-loop hydroponics, in particular, combined with the use of desalinated seawater, significantly reduce the overall environmental impact and enhance water and fertiliser efficiency. Although closed-loop hydroponics require more advanced technology compared to traditional or open-loop systems, they should be viable for many farmers in the region. The

technology is not as complex as high-tech hydroponic greenhouses with lighting and heating, and the higher investment is balanced out by higher returns and lower input costs. However, in the region studied, open-loop hydroponics is currently more common than closed-loop. To reduce the environmental impact and to further increase income, these farmers should install facilities to recirculate drainage water (i.e., closed-loop systems). Additionally, a recycling facility is necessary to allow farmers to recycle the used water on site. If a persistent pest affects tomatoes and prevents the use of the recycled water, farmers can apply the saved water to other crops not impacted by the pest. In total, that would still reduce the impact on the environment. Ultimately, we advocate for the use of closed-loop systems in hydroponic installations to conserve water and lessen the overall environmental impact.

Cherry tomatoes currently generate a higher income and have a higher value added than round tomatoes, presenting a market opportunity for farmers and the country. However, a sudden increase in supply, when many farmers switch to only producing cherry tomatoes, would not only lead to increased pressure on water resources due to the higher water consumed per FU, but could also lead to a subsequent drop in prices. Thus, we recommend diversifying crops on individual farms in order to be able to react to market shocks and seasonality. Further processing, such as producing dried tomatoes or tomato sauce, could add additional value to the country's tomato value chain. However, for these purposes, round tomatoes should be used instead of cherry tomatoes, due to their lower impact on the environment. Finally, exploring organic production or cultivating rare tomato species could open new market opportunities. It should be noted that, optimising crop yields in organic hydroponics to match conventional inorganic hydroponic fertilisation still remains a challenge (Park & Williams, 2024).

Currently, tomatoes from hydroponic production are mainly destined for export, meaning local consumption benefits less from this water-saving technology. Spreading this technology to farmers who produce exclusively for local consumption through knowledge exchange and training is crucial for skill enhancement in the context of the FrontAg Nexus.

The author is concerned about the import and dependency on inputs such as seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides from large institutions like Bayer and Syngenta, particularly for smallholders. These companies promote seeds to overcome issues like ToBRFV; however, such products require high R&D investment, making them more expensive compared to non-resistant varieties. While these solutions appear promising to farmers, they build on a fragile system that

is dependent on high external inputs. Reducing this dependency by developing a stronger local food system, such as by establishing local seed banks, facilitating seed exchanges, adapting pest management practices, and increasing crop diversity, could be beneficial for the livelihoods of local farmers.

5.3 Limitations and future research

This study analysed the tomato value chain in the Souss Massa region of Morocco. The gathered data is a valid representation of tomato cultivation and processes in the region, as similar practices are employed throughout. However, it is limited to a small number of farmers, which reduces the reliability of the data quality. The numbers used for the LCA are averages quoted by the farmers, not exact figures recorded from recent years, which reduces the accuracy of the results. Although using average numbers introduces some uncertainty, supplementing the data with literature values would likely have been less accurate. However, one advantage of this study is that information was collected on the majority of inputs, and the data is valid for the current time period, making the life cycle inventory robust. Details on pesticide use were limited to literature values, which show high discrepancies (e.g., Ecoinvent v3.10; Martínez et al., 2024; Romero-Gómez et al., 2017), thus reducing the data quality in this area. The reliance on literature values increases the uncertainty in the data for traditional cultivation systems. Additionally, for the economic analysis, we did not have access to the farmers' balance sheets. This is partially offset by the fact that the agricultural expert provided some estimations on which we were able to base our assumptions. Access to actual reported data would enhance accuracy. Moreover, the scope of the study limited the inclusion of other important aspects such as social sustainability, the impact on biodiversity or the role of smallholders.

Future research could replicate and expand this study on a larger scale, providing more robust data. Including actual reported numbers from balance sheets would improve the data quality and reliability of the economic analysis. Moreover, for the environmental analysis, researchers could measure and record all input and output data over an entire crop cycle to enhance data quality. However, such an assessment is very time-consuming and expensive. If these resources are not available, a more precise analysis of pesticide use would also be beneficial, as existing literature presents a wide range of values that differ substantially (e.g., Ecoinvent v3.10; Martínez et al., 2024; Romero-Gómez et al., 2017). Furthermore, the methodological baseline for assessing emissions to air from agriculture in hydroponics

requires further development by LCA experts. Additionally, the study shows that it is important to not only focus on round tomatoes in research but also consider the impact of cherry tomatoes. We find that farmers tend to shift from producing round tomatoes to producing cherry tomatoes due to their economic benefits. It would be interesting to observe if there is also a shift in consumption, and if so, to analyse what drives it, as it has direct environmental impacts.

A major issue in production, as we show in the functional analysis, is vulnerability to pests and diseases. While installing suitable water recycling facilities may partially address this issue, future research should focus on finding solutions to mitigate this vulnerability in monocultures and increase resilience. This could include, for instance, diversification in greenhouses and natural pest management. As a next step, future studies could compare the environmental and economic impacts of the latter idea with monoculture hydroponic systems. Moreover, the research should also include smallholders to understand their role and integration within the agri-food system.

6 Conclusion

The goal of this thesis was to analyse an agri-food value chain and to understand and quantify the economic and environmental factors of hydroponics. This study uses hydroponic tomato farming in Morocco as a case study. The methodology follows the VCA4D framework.

The results point out that hydroponic tomato production in Morocco is embedded in a well-organised and structured value chain integrated into the European tomato market, with Morocco being the main non-EU supplier to the EU (European Commission, 2024). The study shows that hydroponic tomatoes are a crucial export product and income source for farmers and the national economy. The comparison indicates that Morocco's low labour costs and favourable climatic conditions make it highly competitive on the international market. This explains Morocco's position as the third-largest exporter of tomatoes worldwide after Mexico and the Netherlands (European Commission, 2024). Moreover, we find that hydroponic installations reduce water footprints and have the potential to increase revenues compared to intensive traditional tomato cultivation due to higher productivity in the controlled system. In particular, closed-loop hydroponics significantly reduces the overall environmental impact and improves water and fertiliser efficiency. However, hydroponic open-loop systems have similar overall

environmental impacts compared to intensive traditional cultivation systems, except that they offer an advantage in water usage. Among the different cases analysed, cherry tomatoes yield the highest profitability for farmers but have the highest environmental footprint.

The importance of this study lies in showing that hydroponics only has a lower environmental impact compared to traditional in soil systems if the system is closed-loop. Open-loop systems are superior regarding the water footprint compared to traditional cultivation, which is important in arid regions but should not be considered in isolation. A measure could be to equip all existing open-loop systems with recirculating possibilities. In addition, our analysis shows that hydroponics allows to produce a product demanded on the international market, so that increasing export opportunities bring important income to individual farmers and to the country. Beyond that, the study provides transparency on economic and environmental sustainability in the agri-food value chain analysed.

In conclusion, hydroponics offers technical solutions to address certain environmental challenges, opens market opportunities, and has the potential to increase revenues compared to cultivation in soil. However, market fluctuations and susceptibility to pests and diseases remain a pressure in the current system.

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Appendices

List of Appendices

Appendix A: Economic analysis	XX
Appendix B: Life cycle inventory	XXIV
Appendix C: Results LCA.....	XXXI
Appendix C.1: Environmental impact of 1m ³ irrigation according to ReCiPe 2016..	XXXI
Appendix C.2: Midpoint results of the four cases according to ReCiPe 2016	XXXII
Appendix C.3: Contribution of the individual processes of the value chain to the midpoint categories.....	XXXIV
Appendix C.4: Sensitivity analysis of transport	XXXV
Appendix C.5: Environmental impact of 1m ³ irrigation according to IPCC	XXXVI
Appendix D: Questionnaire.....	XXXVII

Appendix A: Economic analysis

Table 13: List of expenses and revenues generated in one harvesting season to calculate the GOP of a farm business

Expense	Calculation	Unit	Case 1: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system	Case 2: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, closed-loop system	Case 3: Traditional tomato production in soil in Morocco	Case 4: Hydroponic cherry tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system
Canarian plastic greenhouse ¹⁾	Cost of rent for one hectare of plastic greenhouse	MAD	70'000	70'000	70'000	70'000
	Plastic cover: 1400kg * 32 MAD/kg	MAD	44'800	44'800	44'800	44'800
Substrate ²⁾	<p>25 MAD for one substrate bag, 3000 sac / 1ha are needed: $3000 * 25 = 75'000$ MAD/ha</p> <p>The raspberry farmers pay 30'000 - 40'000 MAD / ha for the substrate from the tomato producer.</p> <p>$75'000 - [30'000, 40'000] = [45'000, 35'000]$ MAD / ha = [min, max]</p>	MAD	45'000	45'000	0	45'000
Seedlings	<p>Tomato round: 3.7 - 5 MAD/plant</p> <p>14'000 plants / ha: $14'000 * 3.7 = 51'800$ MAD/ha, $14'000 * 5 = 70'000$ MAD/ha</p> <p>[min, max] = [51'800, 70'000 MAD/ha]</p> <p>Cherry tomato : 8 - 13 MAD/plant 14'000 plants / ha: $14'000 * 8 = 112'000$ MAD, $14'000 * 13 = 182'000$</p> <p>[min, max] = [112'000, 182'000 MAD/ha]</p>	MAD	70'000	70'000	70'000	182'000

Water	Well water: 2 MAD/m3 Case 1 and 4: 2 MAD * 7875 m3 Case 2: 2 MAD * 5512.5 m3 Case 3: 2 MAD * 9450 m3	MAD	15750	11'025	18'900	15'750
Fertiliser	Costs per hectare	MAD	97'750	68'425	139'911	97'750
Plant protection	Costs per hectare Assumption: For Cherry Tomato 50% more	MAD	65'750	65'750	65'750	98'625
Paid labour costs	Costs per hectare Assumption: For Cherry Tomato 50% more	MAD	90'000	90'000	90'000	135'000
Management fees	Costs related to the organisation and management of the harvest season	MAD	18'000	18'000	18'000	18'000
Transport to commissioning station		MAD	8'500	8'500	8'500	8'500
Extra costs for hydroponics (e.g., rope, bio-stimulation)		MAD	10'000	10'000		10'000
Closed-loop installation		MAD		10'000		
Other costs traditional cultivation (e.g., mulching, tillage, ...)		MAD			15'000	
Financing costs	Annual loan estimated based on the total yearly expense. 5% interest on the loan (Agricbank, 2024).	MAD	26'778	25'575	27'043	36'271
Total costs per hectare		MAD/ha	562'328	537'075	567'904	761'696
Total costs per square meter		MAD/m2	56	54	57	76
Yield		kg/ha	250'000	250'000	234'000	150'000
Total costs per kg		MAD/kg	2.25	2.15	2.43	5.08
Revenue of exported harvest	Expected yearly export per hectare in kg (70% of total harvest)	kg	175'000	175'000	163'800	105'000
Revenue of harvest sold on local market	The remaining of what is not exported (30% of harvest)	kg	75'000	75'000	70'200	105000

Revenue of Export	Considering the average producer price of 3.05 MAD/kg for round tomatoes (FAO, 2024). And 6 MAD/kg for Cherry Tomatoes (pessimistic scenario)	MAD	533'750	533'750	499'590	630'000
Local Revenue	Producer price of 2 MAD/kg for the harvest sold locally	MAD	150000	150000	140400	315000
Total Revenue per hectare		MAD/ha	683'750	683'750	639'990	945'000
Total Revenue per square meter		MAD/m2	68.375	68.375	63.999	94.5
GOP per hectare	Revenue - Costs	MAD/ha	121'423	146'675	72'086	183'304
GOP MAD per square meter	MAD/m2	MAD/m2	12.14	14.67	7.21	18.33
GOP in \$ per hectare	Average exchange rate (MAD to USD: 0.100559) for the last 6 months (Investing.com, 05.06.2024) ---> 0.10	USD/ha	12'142	14'668	7'209	18'330

Note:

- 1) In this analysis, we assume constant economies of scale for the cost of the greenhouse. This means that we treat the greenhouse cost as a fixed yearly expense.
- 2) As explained in Chapter 4.2.1, currently, the farmers can use the substrate for only one year due to the virus. They can sell the used substrate to raspberry farms after the season and recoup part of their initial investment. This results in an annual investment in substrate of 45'000.

Unless otherwise specified, the numbers are derived from the estimates provided by the local agricultural expert. If a bandwidth of costs is given, we use the highest value to ensure that our calculations do not overestimate the profit.

No subsidies were included in the calculations, as the fixed rate per hectare was an exception in the previous year. Normally, farmers do not receive any fixed subsidies per hectare for tomato cultivation.

Table 14: Total costs of the value chain assessed including agricultural costs, packaging and transport

Expense	Unit	Case 1: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system	Case 2: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, closed-loop system	Case 3: Traditional tomato production in soil in Morocco	Case 4: Hydroponic cherry tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system
Agricultural Costs	MAD/kg	2.25	2.15	2.43	5.08
Packaging	MAD/kg	2.50	2.50	2.50	4.00
Transport	MAD/kg	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Total Costs	MAD/kg	6.75	6.65	6.93	11.08

Appendix B: Life cycle inventory

Table 15: Complete life cycle inventory of the LCA

		Unit	Case 1: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, open-loop system	Case 2: Hydroponic tomato production in Morocco, closed-loop system	Case 3: Traditional tomato production in soil in Morocco	Case 4: Hydroponic cherry tomato production in Morocco, open- loop system	Comment on the calculation	References
Outputs to technosphere								
FU	kg	1	1	1	1	1		
Inputs from nature								
Occupation, annual crop	m2a	0.04	0.04	4.27E-02	6.67E-02	Measured in [m2y], land occupation is calculated by multiplying the occupied area by time. Land occupation starts after the harvest of the previous crop (average harvest date) and ends with the harvest of the considered crop. (Nemecek et al., 2023)	--> 1 / Yield	Nemecek et al. (2023)
Transformation, from arable land, unspecified use	m2	0.04	0.04	4.27E-02	6.67E-02	Land transformation: 1 m2 divided by yield/m2		Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Transformation, to arable land, unspecified use	m2	0.04	0.04	4.27E-02	6.67E-02	Land transformation: 1 m2 divided by yield/m2		Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Inputs from technosphere								

Agricultural phase	adjusted: Tomato seedling, for planting {ES} market for tomato seedling, for planting Cut-off, U	plant	5.60E-02	5.60E-02	5.98E-02	9.33E-02	Seedlings produced in Morocco, not heated greenhouse. Average distance to farm 20km. Transport: 100g per seedling incl. pot and boxes (Stoessel et al., 2012) --> 100g*20km*1/1000000 Plant density/ha: 14000 Yield 1: 250'000 kg/ha Yield 2: 250'000 kg/ha Yield 3: 234'000 kg/ha Yield 4: 150'000 kg/ha Amount of plants --> 1400/Yield	Yield: Case 1,2 and 4: Interviews Case 3: Payen et al. (2015) Weight seedling: Stoessel et al. (2012) Distance to farm, plant density: Interviews
	adjusted: Coconut, dehusked {IN} market for coconut, dehusked Cut-off, U	kg	4.80E-02	4.80E-02	0.00E+00	8.00E-02	Coconut Fibres Origin: India or Sri Lanka (Brand: KASP or Botanicoir) --> 3000 bag/ha * 16kg/bag / Yield / 4 years	Interviews
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	kg	6.95E-04	6.95E-04	0.00E+00	1.16E-03	Plastic for the substrate: 694.7 kg plastic /ha --> 694.7 kg/ha / Yield / 4 years	Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)

adjusted: Irrigation {MA} irrigation, drip Cut-off, U	m3	3.15E-02	2.21E-02	4.04E-02	5.25E-02	<p>Drip irrigation: For 1a, 2a, 3 and 4 only well / groundwater</p> <p>For 1b and 2b: 60 % well water, 40 % desalinated water from Agadir (seawater reverse osmosis RO) Electricity source: 60% solar panels, 40% electricity mix (1/3 had no solar panels)</p> <p>Water use: Case 1: 7875 t/ha (--> 25l/d) Case 2: 5512.5 t/ha (30% saving compared to 1) Case 3: 9450 t/ha (--> 30l/d) Case 4: 7875 t/ha (--> 25l/d)</p> <p>--> water use / yield</p>	Interviews
Tillage, ploughing {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	ha	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	4.27E-06	0.00E+00	<p>Tillage only for traditional cultivation: ha per FU --> 1 / Yield (in t)</p>	Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
adjusted: Greenhouse, plastic walls and roof {GLO} market for greenhouse, plastic walls and roof Cut- off, U	m2a	4.00E-02	4.00E-02	4.27E-02	6.67E-02	<p>20 years lifetime, Insect net (sides), plastic (roof), steel</p> <p><i>1 ha divided by the yield in kg/ha. Note: greenhouse dataset stands for 1 m2 used over 1 year</i> --> 10'000 m2 / Yield</p>	Interviews; Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)

Transport, tractor and trailer, agricultural {RoW} market for transport, tractor and trailer, agricultural Cut-off, U	tkm	1.62E-03	1.62E-03	1.51E-03	9.69E-04	On-farm transport: Yield (in tonnes) multiplied by the average distance from field to farm.	Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Pesticide, unspecified {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	kg	1.96E-04	1.96E-04	1.96E-04	1.96E-04		Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Application of plant protection product, by field sprayer {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	ha	1.21E-05	1.21E-05	1.21E-05	1.21E-05		Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Total fertiliser N	kg	4.98E-03	3.48E-03	4.14E-03	8.30E-03	Total NPK: 1244-668-1224 (Expert estimation for NPK usage in the region for tomato production in hydroponics) --> Fertiliser composition calculated according to Kägi et al. (2021)	Case 1, 2, 4: Interviews Case 3: Payen et al. (2015) Calculation according to Kägi et al. (2021)
Total fertiliser P	kg	2.67E-03	1.87E-03	3.32E-03	4.45E-03		
Total fertiliser K	kg	4.90E-03	3.43E-03	1.05E-02	8.16E-03		
Packaging, for pesticides {GLO} market for packaging, for pesticides Cut-off, U	kg	3.92E-04	3.92E-04	3.92E-04	3.92E-04	The total amount of active substance/s is doubled in order to account for the packaging of the diluted product of fertiliser/s that is/are applied. --> 2* 1.96E-04	Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)

	Packaging, for fertilisers {GLO} market for packaging, for fertilisers Cut-off, U	kg	2.51E-02	1.76E-02	3.59E-02	4.18E-02	The total amount of active substance/s is doubled in order to account for the packaging of the diluted product of fertiliser/s that is/are applied (Ecoinvent 3.10). Case 1: 1.25E-02 kg/FU Case 2: 8.78E-03 kg/FU Case 3: 1.80E-02 kg/FU Case 4: 8.16E-03 kg/FU --> total * 2	Calculation according to Ecoinvent v3.10 (2023)
Post-harvest processing phase	Tap water {RoW} market for Cut-off, U	kg	4.00E-01	4.00E-01	4.00E-01	4.00E-01	Water for washing the tomatoes: It was assumed that 0.4 L of tap water is used per kg of crop (Stoessel et al., 2012)	Stoessel et al. (2012)
	Electricity, medium voltage {MA} market for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	kWh	1.43E-03	1.43E-03	1.43E-03	1.43E-03	Energy for sorting and washing: 1.43 kWh / tonne (Bosona et al., 2018)	Bosona et al. (2018)
	Operation, reefer, cooling {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	kg*day	5.00E-01	5.00E-01	5.00E-01	5.00E-01	Overnight storage at commissioning station (4-6°C): --> 1kg for 12h = 0.5 kg*day	Interviews
	Polyethylene, high density, granulate, recycled {Europe without Switzerland} market for polyethylene, high density, granulate, recycled Cut-off, U	g	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	4.00E+01	Extra packaging cherry tomatoes: 10g plastic per 250g of tomato (measured from cherry tomatoes bought in a Swiss supermarket) --> 4*10g = 40 g/FU	Own calculation

	Solid bleached and unbleached board carton {RER} market for solid bleached and unbleached board carton Cut-off, U	g	5.17E+01	5.17E+01	5.17E+01	5.17E+01	Packaging: 1 carton is 310g for 6kg of tomatoes, measured in the commissioning centre --> 310/6 = 51.67 g/FU	Own calculation
Distribution	Transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, euro3 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3 Cut-off, U	tkm	1.50E-02	1.50E-02	1.50E-02	1.50E-02	Transport farm to commissioning centre (15km) Assumption: Euro 3, 3.5-7.5 metric ton --> 1kg Tomato * 15km = 0.015 tkm The climate condition (to 20 degrees Celcius) in the vehicle is neglected, as well as the plastic boxes.	Interviews
	Transport, freight, lorry with reefer, cooling {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	tkm	8.41E-01	8.41E-01	8.41E-01	8.41E-01	Transport from commissioning Centre to Tangier in a lorry with refrigeration (800km) --> (1kg Tomato + packaging) * 800 km = 0.8413tkm	Interviews
Emissions from agricultural phase	Emissions to air							
	Ammonia	kg	7.37E-04	0.00E+00	6.13E-04	1.23E-03	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
	Carbon dioxide, fossil	kg	1.84E-03	0.00E+00	1.53E-03	3.07E-03	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
	Dinitrogen monoxide	kg	2.49E-05	0.00E+00	2.07E-05	4.15E-05	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
	Nitrogen oxides	kg	1.99E-04	0.00E+00	1.65E-04	3.32E-04	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
	Water/m3	m3	2.74E-02	1.92E-02	3.51E-02	4.57E-02	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
	Emissions to water							
Nitrate	kg	2.75E-01	0.00E+00	2.94E-01	2.08E-03	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)		
Phosphate	kg	1.25E-03	0.00E+00	1.71E-03	4.58E-01	Calculation accodring to Nemecek et al. (2023)		

Phosphate	kg	1.87E-04	0.00E+00	2.32E-04	3.12E-04	Calculation according to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
Water, surface	m3	2.44E-03	1.71E-03	3.12E-03	4.06E-03	Calculation according to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
Water, groundwater	m3	6.09E-04	4.26E-04	7.81E-04	1.02E-03	Calculation according to Nemecek et al. (2023)	
Emissions to soil							
Fungicides, unspecified	kg	1.73E-04	0.00E+00	1.73E-04	1.73E-04	100% emission in soil from pesticides according to Ecoinvent 3.10 (2023)	
Insecticides, unspecified	kg	2.30E-05	0.00E+00	2.30E-05	2.30E-05	100% emission in soil from pesticides according to Ecoinvent 3.10 (2023)	

Appendix C: Results LCA

Appendix C.1: Environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to ReCiPe 2016

Irrigation 1: 100% well water, 100% electricity from grid

Irrigation 2: 100% desalinated water, 100% electricity from grid

Irrigation 3: 100% well water, 100% solar energy

Irrigation 4: 100% desalinated water, 100% solar energy

Figure 8: Relative environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to ReCiPe 2016

Table 16: Absolute environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to ReCiPe 2016

Damage category	Unit	Irrigation 1	Irrigation 2	Irrigation 3	Irrigation 4
Human health	DALY	1.09E-06	1.07E-06	7.27E-07	8.46E-07
Ecosystems	species.yr	2.05E-08	1.31E-08	1.99E-08	1.27E-08
Resources	USD2013	2.51E-02	2.52E-02	2.26E-02	2.46E-02

Appendix C.2: Midpoint results of the four cases according to ReCiPe 2016

Figure 9: Relative environmental impacts to each midpoint category for all cases according to ReCiPe 2016

Table 17: Absolute environmental impacts to each midpoint category for all cases according to ReCiPe 2016

Impact category	Unit	Case 1a	Case 1b	Case 2a	Case 2b	Case 3	Case 4
Global warming	kg CO2 eq	3.06E-01	3.04E-01	2.92E-01	2.91E-01	2.96E-01	4.43E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	4.12E-07	4.13E-07	2.35E-07	2.35E-07	2.47E-07	6.54E-07
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	2.32E-02	2.32E-02	2.30E-02	2.30E-02	2.33E-02	3.18E-02
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	1.42E-03	1.42E-03	1.20E-03	1.20E-03	1.31E-03	1.87E-03
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	2.19E-04	2.18E-04	2.16E-04	2.16E-04	2.20E-04	3.18E-04
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	1.45E-03	1.45E-03	1.23E-03	1.23E-03	1.34E-03	1.91E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO2 eq	3.10E-03	3.08E-03	1.58E-03	1.57E-03	2.53E-03	5.01E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	6.68E-04	6.66E-04	1.88E-04	1.87E-04	8.27E-04	1.12E-03
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.85E-02	1.85E-02	5.36E-05	5.36E-05	1.97E-02	3.08E-02
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.19E+00	1.19E+00	1.17E+00	1.17E+00	1.18E+00	1.53E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.50E-02	1.45E-02	1.43E-02	1.40E-02	1.34E-02	2.56E-02
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.63E-03	4.52E-03	4.45E-03	4.37E-03	4.28E-03	7.81E-03
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.09E-04	2.08E-04	2.06E-04	2.05E-04	1.90E-04	2.97E-04
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.74E-03	9.63E-03	9.48E-03	9.40E-03	9.63E-03	1.35E-02
Land use	m2a crop eq	1.81E-01	1.81E-01	1.81E-01	1.81E-01	1.49E-01	2.36E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.13E-03	2.13E-03	2.10E-03	2.11E-03	2.18E-03	3.52E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	8.70E-02	8.67E-02	8.51E-02	8.48E-02	8.50E-02	1.19E-01
Water consumption	m3	3.17E-02	1.91E-02	2.31E-02	1.43E-02	3.94E-02	5.24E-02

Appendix C.3: Contribution of the individual processes of the value chain to the midpoint categories

Table 18: Contribution of the individual processes of the value chain to the midpoint categories using the example of case 1a

Impact category	Unit	Total	Agricultural Phase					Post-harvest processing		Transport
			Agricultural Production	Greenhouse	Fertiliser and Pesticides	Substrate	Irrigation	Processing	Packaging	Distribution
Global warming	kg CO2 eq	2.81E-01	1.20E-02	7.02E-02	1.91E-02	1.92E-02	9.78E-03	1.28E-02	3.19E-02	1.06E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.21E-07	2.74E-07	1.98E-08	2.50E-08	2.15E-07	2.89E-09	6.59E-09	2.49E-08	5.25E-08
	kBq Co-60 eq									
Ionizing radiation	eq	2.43E-02	2.52E-05	3.43E-03	1.17E-03	4.29E-04	3.56E-04	3.73E-04	1.67E-02	1.83E-03
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	1.42E-03	2.03E-04	1.64E-04	6.30E-05	1.08E-04	2.71E-05	1.03E-04	1.35E-04	6.18E-04
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	8.02E-04	2.01E-04	1.85E-04	6.34E-05	7.34E-05	2.28E-05	2.85E-05	6.28E-05	1.66E-04
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	1.45E-03	2.03E-04	1.72E-04	6.42E-05	1.12E-04	2.76E-05	1.04E-04	1.39E-04	6.30E-04
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO2 eq	3.10E-03	1.52E-03	3.22E-04	2.01E-04	4.17E-04	5.91E-05	6.12E-05	1.50E-04	3.66E-04
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	6.68E-04	4.74E-04	9.12E-05	9.92E-06	2.01E-05	1.69E-05	3.48E-06	3.10E-05	2.11E-05
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.85E-02	1.85E-02	6.90E-06	1.39E-06	4.09E-05	4.38E-07	1.88E-07	2.71E-06	1.34E-06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.25E+00	3.18E-03	4.98E-01	1.59E-01	1.27E-01	9.22E-02	1.02E-01	1.87E-01	2.09E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.61E-02	4.04E-05	6.34E-03	1.10E-03	2.63E-03	2.04E-03	4.36E-04	1.48E-03	2.00E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.10E-02	5.30E-05	8.60E-03	1.45E-03	1.91E-03	2.57E-03	6.24E-04	1.99E-03	3.75E-03
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.77E-02	8.72E-05	4.66E-02	1.11E-03	1.47E-03	8.93E-04	9.57E-04	2.53E-03	4.14E-03
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.21E-01	1.92E-03	1.18E-01	2.59E-02	3.28E-02	2.41E-02	1.08E-02	3.56E-02	7.11E-02
Land use	m2a crop eq	1.81E-01	4.05E-02	1.84E-03	1.48E-03	3.55E-02	1.75E-04	3.79E-04	9.37E-02	7.74E-03
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2.97E-03	5.94E-06	1.88E-03	3.98E-04	1.17E-04	6.10E-05	4.00E-05	2.57E-04	2.03E-04
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	8.70E-02	7.47E-04	2.07E-02	6.79E-03	5.00E-03	3.04E-03	4.04E-03	1.03E-02	3.64E-02
Water consumption	m3	3.17E-02	-3.00E-03	9.09E-04	4.10E-04	4.53E-04	3.16E-02	4.26E-04	6.96E-04	1.96E-04

Appendix C.4: Sensitivity analysis of transport

Figure 10: Sensitivity Analysis of transport with and without refrigeration (relative values)

Table 19: Sensitivity Analysis of transport with and without refrigeration (absolute values)

Damage category	Unit	Case 1a, with refrigeration	Case 1a, no refrigeration
Human health	DALY	1.04E-06	9.41E-07
Ecosystems	species.yr	4.33E-09	4.11E-09
Resources	USD2013	3.21E-02	2.83E-02

Appendix C.5: Environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to IPCC

Irrigation 1: 100% well water, 100% electricity from grid

Irrigation 2: 100% desalinated water, 100% electricity from grid

Irrigation 3: 100% well water, 100% solar energy

Irrigation 4: 100% desalinated water, 100% solar energy

Figure 11: Relative environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to IPCC

Table 20: Absolute environmental impact of 1m³ irrigation according to IPCC

Damage category	Unit	Irrigation 1	Irrigation 2	Irrigation 3	Irrigation 4
GWP100	kg CO ₂ -eq	3.07E-01	3.09E-01	2.02E-01	2.47E-01

Appendix D: Questionnaire

Consent:

Before we proceed with this survey, we would like to obtain your consent.

Of course, we will handle your data confidentially and we will not disclose the name of the company you are associated with. Do you agree to participate voluntarily and to share the relevant data with us?

Date:

Signature:

Background of the tomato farm

Name of the organisation:

Code name:

Employment position of the interviewee:

Before we begin, we would like to ask you about the number of employees in your company and the m² / hectares land you are cultivating.

Number of employees:

Size of the farm in hectares/m²:

FQ1: Functional Analysis

Now we will continue with the description of products and stages involved in the production on your farm.

Agricultural Phase:

1. What products are you producing on the farm?
2. What kind of tomatoes varieties are you growing? [exact name]
3. What is the year in which you started to grow tomatoes under hydroponic/soilless conditions?

4. Tell us more about the value chain of those hydroponic/soilless tomatoes. What are the steps from the raw material purchasing until the products leave the farm?
5. How does the operation on the farm look like in detail? Which processes are involved? (Planting the seedlings, irrigation, fertilising, plant protection)

Packaging, Storage and Transport Phase:

6. Do you need to wash the tomatoes before delivering? Where are they washed? Who takes care of this operation (farm or another organisation)?
7. Do you have facilities for storage before transport? Do you have a refrigerator? In what temperature do you store the tomatoes?
8. Is the tomato packaged? [if yes] Where is the packing taking place? Who takes care of this operation (farm or another organisation)?
9. Where are the tomatoes dispatched to after the production (and packaging)? Name the location and/or the organisation.
10. Do you deliver it there by yourself or through a third party? What is the mean of transport used?
11. Who buys the tomatoes? (middle party, retail, ...)

Retail:

12. According to your knowledge, which share of your tomato production is consumed locally? What is the share of export?
[if export, yes]. Do you know, where the exports are mainly going to (country XYZ)?
Do you know total numbers?
13. [if export, yes] From which port are the tomatoes exported? Is there any aircraft transportation involved? Is the export distribution similar to other tomato producer?

Other products:

14. [if any other products on the farm] Do you produce other products in the same greenhouse?
[if yes in the same greenhouse] How do the steps of the hydroponic tomato production differ to the one of the other products of the farm?

Actors:

15. Which actors (e.g., firms, retail, (government), etc.) are involved in the described value chain which we have not mentioned before? And what do they do?
16. Is your tomato production subject to any kind of certification?
17. Is your farm subject to any particular technical/environmental regulations/controls?

Organisation and governance:

18. How does the coordination with the partners and other entities engaged work? How do you communicate? Do you have certain tools in place?
19. How is the relationship/dependency of your farm specifically to other actors?

20. Do you face easy or difficult access to services and inputs? Do other actors give you economic pressure (e.g., trader)? Which actor has highest leverage on your entity?
21. How is the yearly supply and demand? Are there seasons?
Supply season:
Demand season:
22. Do you have several cultivation cycles a year? [if yes] how many?
23. [if Export] How do you differentiate with other competitors worldwide?
24. [if Export] How do you believe are your prices in comparison to the world market?
(Higher/lower)
25. How do you believe your prices are in comparison to farmers producing in soil?
(Higher/lower)
26. How are your prices evolving in the last 3 years?
27. What is the seasonal variation in price, if any?
28. What support do you get from the government? Subsidies? For what purpose?
29. What part of the costs can you cover with subsidies?

Contextual questions:

1. What is the importance of hydroponic tomatoes for Morocco? How is it part of the “le plan Maroc vert” and of the “generation green”? (water stress)
2. What is the role of small farmers in the agricultural production, in particular in the growth of soilless /hydroponic tomatoes?
3. Which are (other) important players in tomato production?
4. How are farmers organised?
5. What kind of subsidies (for outputs/inputs) or other support (e.g. by extension officers, producer cooperatives, contracting organisation if any etc.) do farmers or the industry get? (Do farmers have tax disadvantages or advantages?)
6. How are the Supplier, Producer, Trader relationships? How does the structure look like?
7. How is the competition in Morocco and worldwide in the tomato industry?
8. Which player has the highest market power and price margin for example on/in the price? Is there likely a Monopoly or Oligopoly, a company which set/dictates price levels?
9. How do the prices for fertiliser in the last years (affected by the war of Russia and Ukraine) influence the operation and income of Moroccan farmers? How is the pressure?
10. What were the consequences of the COVID-19? Were there other disruptions in the last years?
11. Did the market change in the last years? How? What are the long-term demand trends?
12. Did the demand towards hydroponic tomatoes grow in the last years?
13. Do you experience that consumers care about the way of production?
14. Is there any price difference in prices of hydroponic tomatoes compared to other types of tomatoes? If yes, why do you think that is so? Sustainability? Form? Taste? What are expectations for the future?
15. Do you think, the public supports the production and export of hydroponic tomatoes? Are there supporting or critical voices?

16. How does the export support the economy and the life of local people? Does it harm local food security?
17. In what other ways farmers get support from the government or other entities? Are they facing regulatory restrictions or policies?
18. How is the access to credits from banks?

[Transition to Part 2]

FQ2: Economic Part

1. What are the costs for the production of one square meter or one plant of tomato?
2. Do you believe, is it more or less expensive to produce tomatoes using hydroponics than in standard greenhouses in soil? How much more/less expensive?
3. Which practice is more time consuming?
4. Where do you face higher investment costs? How much more/less?
5. Can you save money on some inputs such as water, mineral fertilisers or pesticides using hydroponics? (maybe they can tell about their experience in soil production)
6. How much less water do you expect to use compared to a production in soil?
7. On which input can you save the most compared to a production in soil?
8. How many kg/tonnes of tomatoes did you produce in the last three years (each year 2023, 2022, 2021)?
9. Do you consider the last three years as good harvest? Why good, why bad?
10. What is the domestic price per kg (or tonne) tomato you get on average? What is the min and the max domestic price you have experienced in the last 3 years?
11. [if export] What is the international price per kg (or tonne) tomato you get on average? What is the min and the max international price experienced in the last 3 years?
12. [if export] Do you know the end price to which your tomatoes are sold on the local markets / in retail to the consumer?

RQ3: LCA

→ The questions may be partly included in Part 1, but they are listed separately here to maintain clarity regarding which data corresponds to each part of the analysis.

1. What kind of tomato varieties are you growing? [exact name]
→ answer in part 1
2. How many square meters/hectares of land are you cultivating?
→ answer in part 1
3. What is the area under hydroponics? And the area of tomatoes grown under hydroponics?
4. Do you grow vertically?
[if yes] How many floors?
And how many square meters is one level?

In the following questions, you have the option to refer to the amounts (kg) produced in a pot (or any fixed amount of pots) or per square meter. Do you have a preference? The unit can also vary between the questions.

5. What was the yield over the past three years? [kg/ha]
→ Answer in part 2
6. How many plants/pots are used per area (density)? [pot amount/m²]
7. How long is the cultivation time (from seed/seedling to harvest)? [days]
8. Do you have several cycles a year? [if yes] how many?
→ Answer in part 1
9. Where is it cultivated? (Coordinates or exact region)
→ Does not need to be asked, only if we do not have the information beforehand
10. What kind of land was it before it was used for tomato production? (dry land, agricultural land for other crops, etc.)
11. Does the production have a certificate? (e.g., organic)
→ Answer in part 1
12. In what agricultural system is the tomato grown? (hydroponic, soilless, monoculture, mixed cultivation, ...)
→ Answer in part 1

In case of mixed cultivation:

13. What are the crops cultivated with the tomato?
14. What's their value? [MAD/kg]
15. What's their yield over the last three years? [kg/ha]

Substrate:

16. What substrate is used? (perlite, rockwool, vermiculture, sand, bark, peat, coconut fibers, soil)
17. How much substrate is used [kg/pot or kg/ha]?
18. Where is the substrate coming from and how is it produced?
19. How many pots/seedlings are used per area? [seedlings amount/ha]
→ as above

Seed/Seedlings:

20. Where do the seeds/seedlings come from or how are they produced?

Irrigation system:

21. How do you irrigate? What is the type of irrigation system (e.g., drip irrigation)?

22. Do you know the amount of water you are applying each day/month? What is the amount of water during one cultivation time or year [m³ or l / ha]? (- How often do you water? How much water do you use each time?)
23. Where does the water come from? type of water (groundwater, surface water, desalinated water, rainwater)
24. What is the energy source used for irrigation? (diesel, solar)

Fertiliser:

25. What kind of fertiliser is used? (Name, ingredients, NPK ratio)
26. How much fertiliser is used during one cultivation time or month/year? [kg or l/ha] (- How often do you fertilise? How much is applied each time?)
27. Do you also use organic fertiliser? What is the compost composed of? Where does it come from? How is it transported?
28. Ideally, a photo of all fertiliser

Weed management:

29. How do you manage weed?
30. What kind of herbicide do you use? (name)
31. How much herbicides are used during one cultivation time/month/year? [kg or l/ha]
32. Ideally, a photo of herbicides

Pesticide:

33. What diseases do you experience?
34. How do you treat diseases?
35. What is the type of pesticide you are using? (organic/non-organic, name, active ingredient)
36. How much pesticide is used during one cultivation time? [kg or l/ha]
37. Ideally, a photo of pesticides
38. What pests do you experience?
39. How do you treat pests?
40. What is the type of pesticide you are using? (organic/non-organic, name, active ingredient)
41. How much pesticide is used during one cultivation time? [kg or l/ha]
42. Ideally, a photo of pesticides

Machinery:

43. What machinery is used for agricultural production? (Type of machinery)
44. For which other crops is the machinery used?
45. How many hours during a week do you use machinery for the tomatoes?
46. Fuel consumption or energy source [kg or l or Watt]
47. How is the harvesting done? (by hand or machine)

Waste products:

48. How much organic waste is produced? (plants) [kg] Where does it end up?
49. How much substrate waste is produced? [kg] Where does it end up?
50. How much wastewater is produced? [m3] Where does it end up? What about the nutrient solution?
51. Do you have container waste? How many containers are thrown away each day/week?
How big is one container (cm)?
52. Does a part stay within the system, for example, through recycling?

Climate in the greenhouse:

53. How do you manage the climate within the greenhouse?
 - MWh for cooling
 - MWh for heating
54. Do you use lighting in the greenhouse?
 - MWh

Source of electricity:

55. What is your source of electricity?
 - Electricity mix
 - Solar panel / agri-photovoltaic
 - Wind power

Do you have details of the greenhouse?

56. What is the size of roof cover/side walls/gable walls in [m2]?
57. What is the material of the greenhouse? (Share of Concrete/Steel/Plastic/plexiglass)
58. What is the planned lifetime of the greenhouse?
59. (- irrigation pipe [m2])

Washing:

60. Do you need to wash the tomatoes?
→ potentially explained in part 1
61. What processes are involved in washing the tomatoes?

Storage Condition:

→ partially answered in part 1

62. Do you have facilities to store before transport? Refrigerator?
63. In what temperature do you store the tomatoes?
64. For how long do you store the tomatoes?

65. What is the maximum time you can store the product?

Packaging:

66. Is the tomato packaged on the farm?

→ (potentially explained in part 1)

67. How is the tomato packaged?

68. Type of material used

69. Amount of material used [kg material/kg tomato]

70. Origin of material

Transport:

71. where is the tomato transported to afterwards? (all steps)

→ evtl. explained in part 1

72. What are the distances in [km] to the local market or to the port for export?

73. What is the type of transport used (lorry, airplane, train, ship, van)?

74. Is the transport refrigerated? What is the temperature?

Statement of Authorship

By submitting the enclosed

- Project
- Literature review
- Course work
- Minor paper
- Bachelor's thesis
- Master's thesis

the student affirms independent completion of the(ir) work without outside help.

The undersigned student declares that all printed and electronic sources used in the text and the bibliography are correctly indicated, i.e., that the work does not contain any plagiarism (no parts that have been taken in whole or in part from another's or his/her own text or from another's or his/her own work without clear identification and without stating the source).

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Location, date:

27.06.2024

Student signature:

